

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training

D4.2 PreMETS platform operational and integration guidelines

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Project: 101108469 — PreMETS — ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PI-ALL-INNO

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Abbreviations and Terminology

Abbreviations	
LMS	Learning Management System
TN	Train-the-Trainer
PM	Predictive Maintenance
CDN	Content Delivery Network

Terminology	

Executive Summary

The PreMETS platform is a state-of-the-art, cloud-based learning environment designed to enhance predictive maintenance training and courses. Built on the Microsoft Azure cloud infrastructure, it enables the seamless integration of external services and tools, promoting a connected learning experience for both instructors and technical professionals.

This paper describes the operational framework and integration guidelines required to successfully implement the PreMETS platform. The platform that is built on Moodle consists of several components, including:

- Core Platform Infrastructure & UX Design: a robust system backbone with an intuitive user interface that allows for easy navigation and an enhanced user experience.
- Teaching Factory guidelines, which allows learners to interact with industry.
- Learning Management System (LMS) integration: The platform embeds training content via SCORM/MOODLE for a seamless training experience.
- Ethical learner analytics tool: This tool captures learner data (background, learning styles, engagement metrics) to personalize learning paths and improve training effectiveness, with an option for users to opt out.
- Skills forecasting tool: By analyzing training needs and skills gaps, the tool predicts workforce needs using classification and scenario methods.
- Microcredential certification tool: The platform integrates microcredential assessment features aligned with Europass digital certificates, ensuring validated certification of acquired skills.

The PreMETS platform serves as a comprehensive and customizable training ecosystem that leverages advanced cloud technologies to support the future of predictive maintenance training. This document provides important guidelines to ensure smooth operations, seamless integrations and an optimized user experience.

1. Introduction

The PreMETS platform is an innovative educational environment built on Moodle, an open-source Learning Management System (LMS). It offers specialized training in two key areas: TN: Train-the-Trainer and WN: Predictive Maintenance. The platform is designed to support both technical expertise and instructional development, providing learners with interactive and engaging educational content. Through a variety of activities—including quizzes, instructional videos, and discussion forums—users can access valuable resources tailored to their individual learning needs.

PreMETS is globally accessible via a Content Delivery Network (CDN), ensuring fast and reliable access across different regions, and it is hosted at Microsoft Azure cloud computing. The platform is multilingual, supporting the following languages: English, German, Italian, Dutch, Romanian, Serbian, and Greek. The platform is accessible at <https://premets-platform.eu> (figure 1).

To enhance the learning experience, PreMETS incorporates adaptive learning methodologies, allowing users to progress at their own pace based on their knowledge level and performance. By leveraging data analytics and user feedback, the platform continuously refines its content and delivery methods to optimize engagement and knowledge retention. This personalized approach ensures that both trainers and technical professionals receive targeted and effective instruction tailored to their specific needs.

PreMETS: Predictive Maintenance Education and Training System

Welcome to the **PreMETS: Predictive Maintenance Education and Training System**. PreMETS is an alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education and training. In PreMETS, collaboration and knowledge sharing are crucial to promote connectivity, inclusivity, innovation, and equal access to high-quality education in Predictive Maintenance.

Predictive Maintenance (PM) is crucial for optimizing economic resources and fundamental infrastructure systems. Its primary function is to foresee and prevent critical infrastructure breakdowns or failures through digital approaches.

This digital education platform contains two educational programs:

1. the **WN: Predictive Maintenance** which integrates both higher education and vocational education standards and
2. the **TN: Train-the-Trainer** for academic, vocational, and corporate levels, enhancing accessibility and effectiveness of PM education.

These courses offer a micro-credential certificate, offering recognition and certification for PM skills for both learners and trainers.

Available courses

TN: Train-the-Trainer

Teacher: PreMETS Administrator

WN: Predictive Maintenance

Teacher: PreMETS Administrator

Site announcements

There are no discussion topics yet in this forum

Upcoming events

There are no upcoming events
[Go to calendar...](#)

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CERTH/IT Hellenic Institute of Transport

The PreMETS Platform was developed and is maintained by the CERTH/IT

Figure 1: Platform's homepage

2. Registration

To access the courses and content on the PreMETS platform, user registration is required (figure 2). Registration is simple and can be completed using email, or by signing up with a Google or Microsoft account (figure 3).

Figure 2: Platform's login page

Steps for Registration:

1. Accept the platform's policies: During registration, a review and accept the platform's Terms of Use, Cookies Policy, and Privacy Policy documents is required.
2. Fill in mandatory fields: The registration form will ask for essential information such as first and last name, country, username, email address, and a password.

The option will be also given to complete a demographic survey that includes fields:

- Nationality
- Gender
- Age range
- Learning difficulties
- Educational level
- Employment status
- Employment sector

Once registration is completed and the email address is verified, users will have access to all the platform's features and content. This includes enrolling in the courses, participating in discussions, and taking part in assessments.

New account

Username ●

The password must have at least 8 characters, at least 1 digit(s), at least 1 lower case letter(s), at least 1 upper case letter(s), at least 1 special character(s) such as *, -, or #

Password ●

Email address ●

Email (again) ●

First name ●

Last name ●

City/town

Country of residence ●

Select a country ▼

▼ **Demographic Information**

The demographic fields provided below are intended exclusively for analytics and research purposes. We assure you that all information submitted will be treated with the utmost confidentiality and will be accessible solely to you. Neither your instructors nor any other users will have access to this data.

By completing these fields, you will significantly contribute to the enhancement of our services. We kindly request that you take a moment to provide this information. Your participation is highly valuable to us. You can update your selections in your profile at any time.

Thank you for your support.

Nationality ●

Prefer not to say ▼

Gender ●

Prefer not to say ▼

Age range ●

Prefer not to say ▼

Learning difficulties ●

Prefer not to say ▼

Educational level ●

Prefer not to say ▼

Employment status ●

Prefer not to say ▼

Employment sector ●

Prefer not to say ▼

Security question ●

I'm not a robot

Create my new account Cancel

● Required

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Figure 3: Platform's registration form

3. Courses

The PreMETS platform offers two primary courses (figure 4): Train-the-Trainer - TN and Predictive Maintenance -WN. Each course is divided into several sections that focus on different aspects of the subject matter.

Available courses

Figure 4: Platform's available courses

TN: Train-the-Trainer

This course is designed to help educators develop effective strategies for delivering training and fostering learner engagement. It is divided into 8 sections, each covering a different element of teaching and learning (figure 5).

- TN1: Learner happiness, motivation, engagement, and performance strategies
- TN2: Reducing the percentage of drop-outs from online education
- TN3: Inclusive and personalized education strategies for online deliveries in higher and vocational education
- TN4: Brain plasticity and learning connections
- TN5: Qualitative and effective open educational resources
- TN6: Ethical learner analytics guidelines for preventive maintenance field
- TN7: Microcredential systems and skill certification
- TN8: (Re)using existing infrastructures and learning resources

WN: Predictive Maintenance

This course focuses on the technical and strategic elements of predictive maintenance, designed for professionals working in technical fields (figure 6). It consists of 6 sections:

- WN1: Holistic predictive maintenance competences
- WN2: Digital skills competences for predictive maintenance
- WN3: Green skills competences for predictive maintenance
- WN4: Resilience competences for predictive maintenance
- WN5: Innovation & entrepreneurship competences
- WN6: Relearning how to learn in a digital environment

The screenshot shows the PreMETS course interface for 'TN: Train-the-Trainer'. The top navigation bar includes 'Home', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Site administration'. A user profile 'PA' and 'Edit mode' toggle are visible. A left sidebar menu lists course sections: General, Announcements, Forum, License, TN1: Learner happiness, motivation, engagement and performance strategies, TN2: Reducing the percentage of drop-outs from online education, TN3: Inclusive and Personalized Education in Predictive Maintenance Strategies for Online Deliveries in Higher and Vocational Education and Beyond, TN4: Brain Plasticity and Learning Connections, TN5: Qualitative & effective open educational resources, TN6: Ethical learner analytics guidelines for preventive maintenance field, TN7: Microcredential systems and skill certification, TN8: (Re)use existing infrastructures and learning resources, and Course Completion. The main content area displays the course title and a list of sections with their respective activity counts and progress indicators (e.g., 0/4, 0/5).

Section Name	Activities	Progress
General		
TN1: Learner happiness, motivation, engagement and performance strategies	5	0 / 4
TN2: Reducing the percentage of drop-outs from online education	5	0 / 4
TN3: Inclusive and Personalized Education in Predictive Maintenance Strategies for Online Deliveries in Higher and Vocational Education and Beyond	5	0 / 4
TN4: Brain Plasticity and Learning Connections	5	0 / 4
TN5: Qualitative & effective open educational resources	6	0 / 5
TN6: Ethical learner analytics guidelines for preventive maintenance field	6	0 / 5
TN7: Microcredential systems and skill certification	6	0 / 5
TN8: (Re)use existing infrastructures and learning resources	6	0 / 5
Course Completion	2	0 / 1

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Figure 5: TN course and its sections

Figure 6: WN course and its sections

Each course section includes (figure 7):

- Video lectures: Each section contains a video explaining key concepts. In some cases, videos feature an instructor presenting the material.
- Course Materials (figure 8): Every section comes with downloadable materials such as booklets, slides, storyboards, and webquests, available in all supported languages.
- Quizzes: Each section features two types of quizzes:
 - Practice Quiz: Includes 5 random questions, where learners receive feedback immediately after submission. No score is recorded for the practice quiz.
 - Final Quiz: Contains 10 random questions from the section content. Feedback is not provided, and learners must achieve a passing grade to progress. This quiz is necessary for course completion.
- Certification: Upon the learning process and passing the final quiz, users are awarded a certificate of completion for that section.

The screenshot displays the PreMETS platform interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Home', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Site administration'. The user profile 'PA' and 'Edit mode' toggle are visible on the right. A sidebar on the left lists various activities, with 'TN6: Ethical learner analytics...' selected. The main content area is titled 'TN6: Ethical learner analytics guidelines for preventive maintenance field'. It features a 'Video Lecture with Instructor' section with a play button and a 'Mark as done' button. Below this is a 'Video Lecture' section, also with a play button and a 'Mark as done' button. At the bottom, there is a list of activities: 'TN6: Material', 'TN6: Practise Quiz', 'TN6: Final Quiz', and 'TN6: "Ethical learner analytics guidelines for preventive maintenance field" Certificate'. Each activity has a 'Mark as done' button and a status indicator.

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Figure 7: TN6 section activities

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Figure 8: TN1 materia folder

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Upon completion of all sections in either the TN or WN course, users will unlock a new section that contains a final comprehensive quiz. This final quiz includes 25 random questions selected from across all sections of the course. Successfully completing the final quiz is required for the learner to receive the final course certification.

After passing the final quiz, learners will receive a certification that includes their full name, course name, section title (if applicable), course name, the issue date, a verification code, and a QR code. The QR code allows

certificates to be verified easily using mobile devices. All certificates can be validated through the PreMETS platform to confirm their authenticity (figure 9).

Figure 9: Example certification

Courses on the PreMETS platform include an announcement board (figure 10) and a discussion forum (figure 11). The announcement board allows instructors or platform administrators to share important updates, notifications, and course-related news with users. The discussion forum provides an interactive space where students can communicate with other learners and instructors, ask questions, exchange ideas, and engage in collaborative learning.

Figure 10: TN course announcements

The screenshot displays the PreMETS platform interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Home', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Site administration'. A user profile 'PA' and an 'Edit mode' toggle are visible on the right. A left-hand sidebar menu is open, showing a tree view of course content under 'General', 'TN1: Learner happiness, moti...', and 'TN2: Reducing the percentag...'. The main content area is titled 'Forum' and shows a discussion titled 'Questions for TN1 - TN4'. The discussion is by 'Afrediti Anagnostopoulou' on 'Tuesday, 15 October 2024, 3:09 PM'. The message content reads: 'Should you have any questions or require further information, please let us know!'. Below the message are links for 'Permalink', 'Edit', 'Delete', and 'Reply'. The forum interface includes options to 'Display replies in nested form', 'Move this discussion to ...', and 'Move'. There are also links to other forum sections: 'Questions for TN5-TN8' and 'Questions for TN5-TN8'. At the bottom of the page, there are logos for the European Union, CERTH (Centre for Research & Technology Hellas), and CERTH/HIT (Hellenic Institute of Transport). Text at the bottom states: 'The PreMETS Project has received funding from ERASMUS2027 programme, ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PI-ALL-INNO call, under grant agreement No. 101108469' and 'The PreMETS Platform was developed and is maintained by the CERTH/HIT'.

Figure 11: TN course forum

4. Platform

The PreMETS platform offers a range of features designed to support both learning and user interaction:

Each registered user has a personalized profile page (figure 12), where they can:

- View and edit personal information (such as name, email address, etc.).
- Download certificates for completed courses.
- Request all data collected by the platform related to their activity.
- Delete personal data: Users can choose to delete their account and all associated data, although doing so will also remove the ability to verify any certifications.

The screenshot displays the PreMETS Administrator profile page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'PreMETS' and links for 'Home', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Site administration'. A user profile icon labeled 'PA' and an 'Edit mode' toggle are also visible. Below the navigation, a 'Reset page to default' button is present. The main content area is titled 'PA PreMETS Administrator' and is divided into several sections:

- User details:** Includes an 'Edit profile' link, email address (support@premets-platform.eu), country of residence (Greece), city/town (Piraeus), timezone (Europe/Athens), country (GR), nationality (Greek), gender (Male), age range (25-34), learning difficulties (None), educational level (Doctorate or higher), employment status (Employed full-time), and employment sector (Information Technology).
- Miscellaneous:** Includes links for Notes, My certificates, Forum posts, Forum discussions, and Learning plans.
- Reports:** Includes links for Today's logs, All logs, Outline report, Complete report, Browser sessions, Grades overview, and Grades.
- Login activity:** Shows 'First access to site' (Friday, 19 July 2024, 3:27 PM) and 'Last access to site' (Monday, 17 March 2025, 1:22 PM).
- Mobile app:** Includes a QR code for mobile app access and 'Last access to site' (Friday, 8 November 2024, 8:03 AM).
- Privacy and policies:** Includes links for Contact the privacy officer, Data requests, Export all of my personal data, and Policies and agreements.
- Course details:** Includes 'Course profiles' for TN: Train-the-Trainer and WN: Predictive Maintenance.

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Figure 12: Profile page example with user's options and information

Global Announcement Board

The platform includes a global announcement board where users can view updates and important notifications posted by platform administrators or course instructors. This feature helps keep users informed about new content, upcoming events, or platform-related news.

Calendar of Events

The calendar displays all relevant events, such as upcoming course deadlines, webinars, and system maintenance schedules (figure 13). Users can access this calendar to stay on top of important dates.

Figure 13: Calendar event example, “WN - Pre-Pilot Timisoara Day 3”

Accessibility and Multilingual Support

PreMETS is designed to be accessibility-friendly, with tools and features verified by external accessibility audits. The platform supports a wide range of accessibility needs, including screen readers and alternative navigation options.

Additionally, users can select their preferred language through the platform’s language menu. While English is fully supported, a significant portion of the platform’s content is translated into other languages. This helps ensure the platform is accessible to users from various linguistic backgrounds.

The platform is governed by three main policies: the Terms of Use, the Cookies Policy, and the Privacy Policy.

- The Terms of Use outlines the rules and guidelines that users must follow when accessing or using the platform. It covers the responsibilities of both the platform and the user, including acceptable behavior, restrictions on usage, and consequences for violating these terms. It also addresses legal considerations such as intellectual property rights, disclaimers, and limitations of liability, essentially serving as an agreement between the user and the platform on how the service can be used.
- The Cookies Policy explains how the platform uses cookies to improve the user experience. Cookies are small text files that are stored on a user’s device and help the platform remember certain details like preferences, login information, or track how the site is being used. This policy details the types of cookies used, the reasons for using them (such as for functionality or marketing), and provides instructions for users on how to manage or disable cookies in their browser settings.
- The Privacy Policy outlines how the platform collects, stores, and protects users’ personal data. It explains the types of personal information that are gathered, such as names, email addresses, or payment details, and how that information is used, whether for improving services or communication. The policy also addresses how the platform might share data with third parties and informs users of their rights to access, update, or delete their personal information.

All policies are listed in the following link: <https://premets-platform.eu/admin/tool/policy/viewall.php>

5. Conclusions

The PreMETS platform is a comprehensive and user-friendly environment that offers high-quality training in Predictive Maintenance. With an intuitive interface, diverse learning resources, and an array of interactive features, PreMETS enables learners to develop critical skills in a collaborative and engaging environment.

By following this manual, users can easily navigate the platform, access courses, complete quizzes, and receive valuable certifications upon course completion. Whether a learner, instructor, or platform administrator, PreMETS provides all the tools necessary for a successful educational experience.

German Version

1. Einleitung

Die PreMETS-Plattform ist eine innovative Bildungsumgebung, die auf Moodle, einem Open-Source-Lernmanagementsystem (LMS), basiert. Sie bietet spezialisierte Ausbildung in zwei Schlüsselbereichen: TN: Train-the-Trainer und WN: Vorausschauende Wartung. Die Plattform ist so konzipiert, dass sie sowohl technisches Fachwissen als auch die Entwicklung von Lehrinhalten unterstützt und den Lernenden interaktive und ansprechende Lerninhalte bietet. Durch eine Vielzahl von Aktivitäten – darunter Quizze, Lehrvideos und Diskussionsforen – können die NutzerInnen auf wertvolle Ressourcen zugreifen, die auf ihre individuellen Lernbedürfnisse zugeschnitten sind.

PreMETS ist weltweit über ein Content Delivery Network (CDN) zugänglich, das einen schnellen und zuverlässigen Zugriff über verschiedene Regionen hinweg gewährleistet, und wird bei Microsoft Azure Cloud Computing gehostet. Die Plattform ist mehrsprachig und unterstützt die folgenden Sprachen: Englisch, Deutsch, Italienisch, Niederländisch, Rumänisch, Serbisch und Griechisch. Die Plattform ist zugänglich unter <https://premets-platform.eu> (Abbildung 1).

Um die Lernerfahrung zu verbessern, beinhaltet PreMETS adaptive Lernmethoden, die es den BenutzerInnen ermöglichen, je nach Wissensstand und Leistung in ihrem eigenen Tempo voranzukommen. Durch die Nutzung von Datenanalysen und Nutzerfeedback verfeinert die Plattform kontinuierlich ihre Inhalte und Vermittlungsmethoden, um das Engagement und die Wissensspeicherung zu optimieren. Dieser personalisierte Ansatz stellt sicher, dass sowohl AusbilderInnen als auch technische Fachkräfte gezielte und effektive, auf ihre spezifischen Bedürfnisse zugeschnittene Schulungen erhalten.

PreMETS: Predictive Maintenance Education and Training System

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2. the **TN: Train-the-Trainer** for academic, vocational, and corporate levels, enhancing accessibility and effectiveness of PM education.

These courses offer a micro-credential certificate, offering recognition and certification for PM skills for both learners and trainers.

Available courses

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Teacher: PreMETS Administrator

WN: Predictive Maintenance

Teacher: PreMETS Administrator

Site announcements

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Upcoming events

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[Go to calendar...](#)

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Abbildung 1: Website der Plattform

2. Anmeldung

Um auf die Kurse und Inhalte der PreMETS-Plattform zugreifen zu können, ist eine Benutzerregistrierung erforderlich (Abbildung 2). Die Registrierung ist einfach und kann per E-Mail oder durch Anmeldung mit einem Google- oder Microsoft-Konto erfolgen (Abbildung 3).

Abbildung 2: Anmeldeseite der Plattform

Schritte zur Registrierung:

1. Akzeptieren Sie die Richtlinien der Plattform: Während der Registrierung müssen Sie die Nutzungsbedingungen, die Cookie-Richtlinie und die Datenschutzrichtlinie der Plattform lesen und akzeptieren.
2. Füllen Sie die Pflichtfelder aus: Im Registrierungsformular werden wichtige Informationen wie Vor- und Nachname, Land, Benutzername, E-Mail-Adresse und ein Passwort abgefragt.

Außerdem haben Sie die Möglichkeit, einen demografischen Fragebogen auszufüllen, der folgende Felder enthält:

- Nationalität
- Geschlecht
- Altersgruppe
- Lernschwierigkeiten
- Bildungsstand
- Beschäftigungsstatus
- Sektor der Beschäftigung

Sobald die Registrierung abgeschlossen und die E-Mail-Adresse verifiziert ist, haben die NutzerInnen Zugang zu allen Funktionen und Inhalten der Plattform. Dazu gehört die Einschreibung in die Kurse, die Teilnahme an Diskussionen und die Teilnahme an Bewertungen.

New account

Username ●

The password must have at least 8 characters, at least 1 digit(s), at least 1 lower case letter(s), at least 1 upper case letter(s), at least 1 special character(s) such as *, -, or #

Password ●

Email address ●

Email (again) ●

First name ●

Last name ●

City/town

Country of residence ●

Select a country ▾

Demographic Information

The demographic fields provided below are intended exclusively for analytics and research purposes. We assure you that all information submitted will be treated with the utmost confidentiality and will be accessible solely to you. Neither your instructors nor any other users will have access to this data.

By completing these fields, you will significantly contribute to the enhancement of our services. We kindly request that you take a moment to provide this information. Your participation is highly valuable to us. You can update your selections in your profile at any time.

Thank you for your support.

Nationality ●

Prefer not to say ▾

Gender ●

Prefer not to say ▾

Age range ●

Prefer not to say ▾

Learning difficulties ●

Prefer not to say ▾

Educational level ●

Prefer not to say ▾

Employment status ●

Prefer not to say ▾

Employment sector ●

Prefer not to say ▾

Security question ●

I'm not a robot

[Create my new account](#) [Cancel](#)

● Required

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Abbildung 3: Anmeldeformular der Plattform

3. Kurse

Die PreMETS-Plattform bietet zwei Hauptkurse an (Abbildung 4): Train-the-Trainer - TN und Predictive Maintenance - WN. Jeder Kurs ist in mehrere Abschnitte unterteilt, die sich auf verschiedene Aspekte des Themas konzentrieren.

Available courses

TN: Train-the-Trainer

Teacher: [PreMETS Administrator](#)

WN: Predictive Maintenance

Teacher: [PreMETS Administrator](#)

Abbildung 4: Verfügbare Kurse auf der Plattform

TN: Train-the-Trainer

Dieser Kurs soll PädagogInnen helfen, effektive Strategien für die Durchführung von Schulungen zu entwickeln und das Engagement der Lernenden zu fördern. Er ist in 8 Abschnitte unterteilt, die jeweils ein anderes Element des Lehrens und Lernens abdecken (Abbildung 5).

- TN1: Zufriedenheit der Lernenden, Motivation, Engagement und Leistungsstrategien
- TN2: Verringerung des Anteils der Studienabbrecher in der Online-Bildung
- TN3: Inklusive und personalisierte Bildungsstrategien für Online-Angebote in der Hochschul- und Berufsbildung
- TN4: Plastizität des Gehirns und Lernzusammenhänge
- TN5: Qualitative und effektive offene Bildungsressourcen
- TN6: Ethische Leitlinien für die Analyse von Lernenden im Bereich der vorbeugenden Instandhaltung
- TN7: Mikrokreditsysteme und Kompetenzzertifizierung
- TN8: (Wieder-)Nutzung bestehender Infrastrukturen und Lernressourcen

WN: Vorausschauende Instandhaltung

Dieser Kurs konzentriert sich auf die technischen und strategischen Elemente der vorausschauenden Instandhaltung und richtet sich an Fachleute, die in technischen Bereichen arbeiten (Abbildung 6). Er besteht aus sechs Abschnitten:

- WN1: Ganzheitliche Kompetenzen für vorausschauende Instandhaltung
- WN2: Digitale Kompetenzen für vorausschauende Instandhaltung
- WN3: Grüne Kompetenzen für die vorausschauende Instandhaltung
- WN4: Resilienzkompetenzen für die vorausschauende Instandhaltung
- WN5: Kompetenzen in den Bereichen Innovation und Unternehmertum
- WN6: Lernen in einem digitalen Umfeld neu lernen

The screenshot shows the PreMETS interface for a course titled "TN: Train-the-Trainer". The top navigation bar includes "Home", "Dashboard", "My courses", and "Site administration". A user profile "PA" and an "Edit mode" toggle are visible in the top right. A left sidebar menu lists various course sections, including "General", "TN1: Learner happiness, motivation, engagement and performance strategies", "TN2: Reducing the percentage of drop-outs from online education", "TN3: Inclusive and Personalized Education in Predictive Maintenance Strategies for Online Deliveries in Higher and Vocational Education and Beyond", "TN4: Brain Plasticity and Learning Connections", "TN5: Qualitative & effective open educational resources", "TN6: Ethical learner analytics guidelines for preventive maintenance field", "TN7: Microcredential systems and skill certification", "TN8: (Re)use existing infrastructures and learning resources", and "Course Completion".

The main content area displays the course details for "TN: Train-the-Trainer". It includes a "General" section with "Announcements" and "Forum" links. Below this, a list of course sections is shown, each with a title, a progress indicator (Activities: X / Y), and a "Progress: 0 / Y" status. The sections are:

- TN1: Learner happiness, motivation, engagement and performance strategies** (Activities: 5, Progress: 0 / 4)
- TN2: Reducing the percentage of drop-outs from online education** (Activities: 5, Progress: 0 / 4)
- TN3: Inclusive and Personalized Education in Predictive Maintenance Strategies for Online Deliveries in Higher and Vocational Education and Beyond** (Activities: 5, Progress: 0 / 4)
- TN4: Brain Plasticity and Learning Connections** (Activities: 5, Progress: 0 / 4)
- TN5: Qualitative & effective open educational resources** (Activities: 6, Progress: 0 / 5)
- TN6: Ethical learner analytics guidelines for preventive maintenance field** (Activities: 6, Progress: 0 / 5)
- TN7: Microcredential systems and skill certification** (Activities: 6, Progress: 0 / 5)
- TN8: (Re)use existing infrastructures and learning resources** (Activities: 6, Progress: 0 / 5)
- Course Completion** (Activities: 2, Progress: 0 / 1)

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Abbildung 5: TN Kurse und ihre Abschnitte

The screenshot shows the PreMETS course interface for 'WN: Predictive Maintenance'. The top navigation bar includes 'Home', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Site administration'. The course title 'WN: Predictive Maintenance' is prominently displayed. Below the title, there are tabs for 'Course', 'Settings', 'Participants', 'Grades', 'Reports', and 'More'. The main content area is divided into several sections, each with a title, a progress indicator, and a right-pointing arrow:

- General**: Includes 'Announcements' and 'Forum'. A note states: 'PreMETS materials are licensed under Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0 International' with the CC BY-NC-ND logo.
- WN1: Holistic PM competences**: Progress: 0 / 4
- WN2: Digital skills competences for PM**: Progress: 0 / 4
- WN3: Green skills competences for PM**: Progress: 0 / 4
- WN4: Resilience competences for PM**: Progress: 0 / 4
- WN5: Innovation & entrepreneurship competences**: Progress: 0 / 4
- WN6: Relearning how to learn in a digital environment**: Progress: 0 / 4
- Completion**: Progress: 0 / 1

A sidebar on the left lists the course structure, including 'General', 'WN1: Holistic PM competences', 'WN2: Digital skills competences...', and 'WN3: Green skills competences for PM'. The sidebar items include 'Video Lecture', 'Material', 'Practise Quiz', and 'Final Quiz'.

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Abbildung 6: WN Kurse und ihre Abschnitte

Jeder Kursabschnitt umfasst (Abbildung 7):

- Video-Vorlesungen: Jeder Abschnitt enthält ein Video, in dem die wichtigsten Konzepte erklärt werden. In einigen Fällen werden die Videos von einem Ausbilder präsentiert.
- Kursmaterialien (Abbildung 8): Zu jedem Abschnitt gibt es herunterladbare Materialien wie Broschüren, Folien, Storyboards und Webquests, die in allen unterstützten Sprachen verfügbar sind.
- Quizze: Jeder Abschnitt enthält zwei Quizarten:
 - Übungsquiz: Enthält 5 zufällige Fragen, bei denen die Lernenden sofort nach der Abgabe ein Feedback erhalten. Für das Praxis-Quiz wird keine Punktzahl aufgezeichnet.
 - Abschluss-Quiz: Enthält 10 zufällige Fragen aus dem Inhalt des Abschnitts. Es gibt keine Rückmeldung, und die Lernenden müssen eine gute Note erreichen, um weiterzukommen. Dieses Quiz ist für den Abschluss des Kurses erforderlich.
- Zertifizierung: Nach Abschluss des Lernprozesses und Bestehen des abschließenden Quiz erhalten die BenutzerInnen ein Zertifikat über den Abschluss des jeweiligen Abschnitts.

PreMETS Home Dashboard My courses Site administration PA Edit mode

TN / TN6: Ethical learner analytics guidelines for preventive maintenance field

TN6: Ethical learner analytics guidelines for preventive maintenance field

Mark as done

Video Lecture with Instructor

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training

Mark as done

Video Lecture

Mark as done

- TN6: Material (Mark as done)
- TN6: Practise Quiz (To do)
- Not available unless: The activity TN6: Video Lecture with instructor is marked complet... (Show more)
- TN6: Final Quiz (To do)
- Not available unless: The activity TN6: Practise Quiz is marked complete
- TN6: "Ethical learner analytics guidelines for preventive maintenance field" Certificate (To do)
- Not available unless: The activity TN6: Final Quiz is marked complete

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Abbildung 7: TN6 Kursabschnitte

The screenshot displays the PreMETS platform interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Home', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Site administration'. The user is logged in as 'PA' and the interface is in 'Edit mode'. The main content area shows the course 'TN / TN1: Learner happiness, motivation, engagement and performance strategies / TN1: Material'. The 'TN1: Material' folder is selected, showing a list of materials organized by language: Deutsch, English, Italiano, Nederlands, Română, Srpski, and Ελληνικά. Each language folder contains four files: TN1-Booklet-*.pdf, TN1-Slides-*.pdf, TN1-Storyboard-*.pdf, and TN1-WebQuest-*.pdf. There is also a 'TN-Videos.pdf' file at the bottom. A 'Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0 International' license logo is visible. A sidebar on the left shows a navigation menu with 'General', 'TN1: Learner happiness, moti...', and 'TN2: Reducing the percentag...'. The 'TN1: Material' item is highlighted in blue.

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Abbildung 8: TN1 Kursmaterialien

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Nach Abschluss aller Abschnitte des TN- oder WN-Kurses wird ein neuer Abschnitt freigeschaltet, der ein abschließendes umfassendes Quiz enthält. Dieses abschließende Quiz enthält 25 zufällig ausgewählte Fragen aus allen Abschnitten des Kurses. Das erfolgreiche Absolvieren des abschließenden Quiz ist Voraussetzung für den Erhalt des abschließenden Kurszertifikats.

Nach Bestehen des abschließenden Quiz erhalten die Lernenden eine Bescheinigung, die ihren vollständigen Namen, den Kursnamen, den Titel des Abschnitts (falls zutreffend), den Kursnamen, das Ausstellungsdatum, einen Verifizierungscode und einen QR-Code enthält. Der QR-Code ermöglicht die einfache Überprüfung der Zertifikate mit mobilen Geräten. Alle Zertifikate können über die PreMETS-Plattform validiert werden, um ihre Authentizität zu bestätigen (Abbildung 9).

Abbildung 9: Beispielzertifikat

Die Kurse auf der PreMETS-Plattform umfassen ein Ankündigungsbrett (Abbildung 10) und ein Diskussionsforum (Abbildung 11). Das Ankündigungsbrett ermöglicht es Lehrkräften oder Plattformadministratoren, wichtige Updates, Benachrichtigungen und kursbezogene Neuigkeiten mit den NutzerInnen zu teilen. Das Diskussionsforum bietet einen interaktiven Raum, in dem Studierende mit anderen Lernenden und Dozenten kommunizieren, Fragen stellen, Ideen austauschen und gemeinsam lernen können.

Abbildung 10: TN Kursankündigungen

The screenshot displays the PreMETS user interface. At the top, the navigation bar includes 'Home', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Site administration'. The user profile 'PA' and 'Edit mode' are visible on the right. A left-hand sidebar menu lists various course components, with 'Forum' highlighted. The main content area shows the forum path 'TN / General / Forum / Questions for TN1 - TN4'. The forum title is 'Questions for TN1 - TN4', and it includes sub-links for 'Forum', 'Settings', 'Advanced grading', 'Subscriptions', 'Reports', and 'More'. A post by 'Afroditi Anagnostopoulou' is shown, dated Tuesday, 15 October 2024, 3:09 PM. The post content asks: 'Should you have any questions or require further information, please let us know!'. Below the post are links for 'Permalink', 'Edit', 'Delete', and 'Reply'. At the bottom of the page, there are logos for the European Union, CERTH (Centre for Research & Technology Hellas), and CERTH/HT (Hellenic Institute of Transport). Text below the logos states: 'The PreMETS Project has received funding from ERASMUS2027 programme, ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PI-ALL-INNO call, under grant agreement No. 101108469' and 'The PreMETS Platform was developed and is maintained by the CERTH/HT'.

Abbildung 11: TN Kursforum

4. Plattform

Die PreMETS-Plattform bietet eine Reihe von Funktionen, die sowohl das Lernen als auch die Interaktion der NutzerInnen unterstützen sollen:

Jeder registrierte Benutzer verfügt über eine personalisierte Profilsseite (Abbildung 12), auf der er Folgendes tun kann:

- Persönliche Informationen (wie Name, E-Mail-Adresse usw.) einsehen und bearbeiten.
- Zertifikate für abgeschlossene Kurse herunterladen.
- Alle von der Plattform gesammelten Daten zu seiner Aktivität abfragen.
- Persönliche Daten löschen: Die NutzerInnen können ihr Konto und alle damit verbundenen Daten löschen, allerdings können dann auch keine Zertifizierungen mehr überprüft werden.

The screenshot shows the user profile page for a PreMETS Administrator. The page is titled "PA PreMETS Administrator" and includes a "Reset page to default" button. The profile details are as follows:

- User details:** Edit profile
- Email address:** support@premets-platform.eu (Visible to everyone)
- Country of residence:** Greece
- City/town:** Piraeus
- Timezone:** Europe/Athens
- Country:** GR
- Nationality:** Greek
- Gender:** Male
- Age range:** 25-34
- Learning difficulties:** None
- Educational level:** Doctorate or higher
- Employment status:** Employed full-time
- Employment sector:** Information Technology

Other sections include:

- Miscellaneous:** Notes, My certificates, Forum posts, Forum discussions, Learning plans
- Reports:** Today's logs, All logs, Outline report, Complete report, Browser sessions, Grades overview, Grades
- Login activity:** First access to site (Friday, 19 July 2024, 3:27 PM (240 days 22 hours)), Last access to site (Monday, 17 March 2025, 1:22 PM (now)), Last IP address (172.71.144.35)
- Mobile app:** QR code for mobile app access (For security reasons login via QR code is not allowed for site administrators or if you are logged in as another user.), Last access to site (Friday, 8 November 2024, 8:03 AM (129 days 5 hours))
- Privacy and policies:** Contact the privacy officer, Data requests, Export all of my personal data, Policies and agreements
- Course details:** Course profiles (TN: Train-the-Trainer, WN: Predictive Maintenance)

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Abbildung 12: Beispiel einer Profilsseite mit Benutzeroptionen und -informationen

Globales Ankündigungsbrett

Die Plattform verfügt über ein globales Ankündigungsbrett, auf dem die NutzerInnen Aktualisierungen und wichtige Mitteilungen von Plattformadministratoren oder KursleiterInnen einsehen können. Mit dieser Funktion können Sie die Benutzer über neue Inhalte, bevorstehende Veranstaltungen oder plattformbezogene Neuigkeiten informieren.

Veranstaltungskalender

Der Kalender zeigt alle relevanten Ereignisse an, wie z. B. bevorstehende Kursabgabetermine, Webinare und Systemwartungspläne (Abbildung 13). Benutzer können auf diesen Kalender zugreifen, um über wichtige Termine auf dem Laufenden zu bleiben.

Abbildung 13: Beispiel Veranstaltungskalender "WN - Pre-Pilot Timisoara Day 3"

Barrierefreiheit und mehrsprachige Unterstützung

PreMETS ist so konzipiert, dass es barrierefrei ist, mit Werkzeugen und Funktionen, die durch externe Zugänglichkeitsprüfungen verifiziert wurden. Die Plattform unterstützt eine breite Palette von Zugänglichkeitsanforderungen, einschließlich Bildschirmlesegeräten und alternativen Navigationsoptionen.

Außerdem können die Nutzer über das Sprachmenü der Plattform ihre bevorzugte Sprache auswählen. Obwohl Englisch vollständig unterstützt wird, ist ein großer Teil des Inhalts der Plattform in andere Sprachen übersetzt. Dies trägt dazu bei, dass die Plattform für NutzerInnen mit unterschiedlichem sprachlichem Hintergrund zugänglich ist.

Die Plattform unterliegt drei Hauptrichtlinien: den Nutzungsbedingungen, der Cookie-Richtlinie und der Datenschutzrichtlinie.

- In den Nutzungsbedingungen sind die Regeln und Richtlinien aufgeführt, die die NutzerInnen beim Zugriff auf die Plattform und bei der Nutzung derselben befolgen müssen. Sie umfassen die Verantwortlichkeiten sowohl der Plattform als auch des Nutzers, einschließlich des akzeptablen Verhaltens, der Nutzungsbeschränkungen und der Konsequenzen bei Verstößen gegen diese Bedingungen. Sie befasst sich auch mit rechtlichen Aspekten wie geistigen Eigentumsrechten, Haftungsausschlüssen und Haftungsbeschränkungen und dient im Wesentlichen als Vereinbarung zwischen dem Nutzer und der Plattform darüber, wie der Dienst genutzt werden kann.
- In der Cookie-Richtlinie wird erläutert, wie die Plattform Cookies verwendet, um die Nutzererfahrung zu verbessern. Cookies sind kleine Textdateien, die auf dem Gerät des Nutzers gespeichert werden und der Plattform helfen, sich an bestimmte Details wie Präferenzen und Anmeldeinformationen zu erinnern oder zu verfolgen, wie die Website genutzt wird. Diese Richtlinie beschreibt die Arten von Cookies, die verwendet werden, die Gründe für ihre Verwendung (z. B. für die Funktionalität oder das Marketing)

und gibt den NutzerInnen Anweisungen, wie sie Cookies in ihren Browsereinstellungen verwalten oder deaktivieren können.

- In der Datenschutzrichtlinie wird dargelegt, wie die Plattform die personenbezogenen Daten der NutzerInnen sammelt, speichert und schützt. Es wird erläutert, welche Arten von personenbezogenen Daten gesammelt werden, wie z. B. Namen, E-Mail-Adressen oder Zahlungsangaben, und wie diese Daten verwendet werden, sei es zur Verbesserung der Dienste oder der Kommunikation. Die Richtlinie geht auch darauf ein, wie die Plattform Daten an Dritte weitergeben kann, und informiert die NutzerInnen über ihre Rechte, auf ihre persönlichen Daten zuzugreifen, sie zu aktualisieren oder zu löschen.

Alle Richtlinien sind unter dem folgenden Link aufgeführt: <https://premets-platform.eu/admin/tool/policy/viewall.php>

5. Schlussfolgerungen

Die PreMETS-Plattform ist eine umfassende und benutzerfreundliche Umgebung, die eine qualitativ hochwertige Ausbildung in der vorausschauenden Instandhaltung bietet. Mit einer intuitiven Benutzeroberfläche, vielfältigen Lernressourcen und einer Reihe von interaktiven Funktionen ermöglicht PreMETS den Lernenden, wichtige Fähigkeiten in einer kooperativen und ansprechenden Umgebung zu entwickeln.

Wenn Sie dieses Handbuch befolgen, können die Benutzer leicht durch die Plattform navigieren, auf Kurse zugreifen, Quizfragen beantworten und nach Abschluss des Kurses wertvolle Zertifizierungen erhalten. Ob Lernende, AusbilderInnen oder Plattformadministratoren, PreMETS bietet alle notwendigen Werkzeuge für eine erfolgreiche Bildungserfahrung.

Italian Version

1. Introduzione

La piattaforma PreMETS è un ambiente educativo innovativo basato su Moodle, un sistema open-source di Learning Management System (LMS). Il sito offre una formazione specializzata in due aree chiave: TN – Train-the-Trainer e WN – Predictive Maintenance. La piattaforma è progettata per supportare sia lo sviluppo di competenze tecniche che la formazione degli istruttori, offrendo contenuti educativi interattivi e coinvolgenti. Attraverso una varietà di attività—tra cui quiz, video didattici e forum di discussione—gli utenti possono accedere a risorse preziose, adattate ai propri bisogni formativi individuali.

PreMETS è accessibile a livello globale grazie a una Content Delivery Network (CDN), che garantisce un accesso rapido e affidabile in diverse regioni ed è ospitata sul cloud computing di Microsoft Azure. La piattaforma è multilingue e supporta le seguenti lingue: inglese, tedesco, italiano, olandese, rumeno, serbo e greco. È accessibile all'indirizzo: <https://premets-platform.eu> (figura 1).

Per migliorare l'esperienza di apprendimento, PreMETS incorpora metodologie di apprendimento adattivo, permettendo agli utenti di progredire secondo i propri ritmi, in base al livello di conoscenza e alle prestazioni. Sfruttando l'analisi dei dati e il feedback degli utenti, la piattaforma affina costantemente i contenuti e le modalità di erogazione, con l'obiettivo di ottimizzare l'engagement e la memorizzazione delle conoscenze. Questo approccio personalizzato garantisce che sia i formatori sia i professionisti tecnici ricevano una formazione mirata ed efficace, adattata ai propri bisogni specifici.

PreMETS: Predictive Maintenance Education and Training System

Welcome to the **PreMETS: Predictive Maintenance Education and Training System**. PreMETS is an alliance for boosting the European innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education and training. In PreMETS, collaboration and knowledge sharing are crucial to promote connectivity, inclusivity, innovation, and equal access to high-quality education in Predictive Maintenance.

Predictive Maintenance (PM) is crucial for optimizing economic resources and fundamental infrastructure systems. Its primary function is to foresee and prevent critical infrastructure breakdowns or failures through digital approaches.

This digital education platform contains two educational programs:

1. the **WN: Predictive Maintenance** which integrates both higher education and vocational education standards and
2. the **TN: Train-the-Trainer** for academic, vocational, and corporate levels, enhancing accessibility and effectiveness of PM education.

These courses offer a micro-credential certificate, offering recognition and certification for PM skills for both learners and trainers.

Available courses

TN: Train-the-Trainer

Teacher: PreMETS Administrator

WN: Predictive Maintenance

Teacher: PreMETS Administrator

Site announcements

There are no discussion topics yet in this forum

Upcoming events

There are no upcoming events
[Go to calendar...](#)

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Figura 14: Homepage della piattaforma

2. Registrazione

Per accedere ai corsi e ai contenuti della piattaforma PreMETS, è necessaria la registrazione dell'utente (figura 2). La procedura è semplice e può essere completata utilizzando un indirizzo email, oppure registrandosi tramite un account Google o Microsoft (figura 3).

Figura 15: Pagina di log in della piattaforma

Passaggi per la registrazione:

1. Accettare le policy della piattaforma: Durante la registrazione, è richiesto di prendere visione e accettare i documenti relativi ai *Termini di Utilizzo*, alla *Cookie Policy* e alla *Privacy Policy*.
2. Compilare i campi obbligatori: Il modulo di registrazione richiede informazioni essenziali quali nome, cognome, paese di provenienza, nome utente, indirizzo email e una password.

Sarà inoltre offerta la possibilità di compilare un questionario demografico, che include i seguenti campi:

- Nazionalità
- Genere
- Fascia d'età
- Difficoltà di apprendimento
- Livello di istruzione
- Stato occupazionale
- Settore lavorativo

Una volta completata la registrazione e verificato l'indirizzo email, gli utenti avranno accesso a tutte le funzionalità e ai contenuti della piattaforma. Ciò include l'iscrizione ai corsi, la partecipazione alle discussioni e lo svolgimento delle valutazioni.

New account

Username ●

The password must have at least 8 characters, at least 1 digit(s), at least 1 lower case letter(s), at least 1 upper case letter(s), at least 1 special character(s) such as *, -, or #

Password ●

Email address ●

Email (again) ●

First name ●

Last name ●

City/town

Country of residence ●

Select a country ▾

Demographic Information

The demographic fields provided below are intended exclusively for analytics and research purposes. We assure you that all information submitted will be treated with the utmost confidentiality and will be accessible solely to you. Neither your instructors nor any other users will have access to this data.

By completing these fields, you will significantly contribute to the enhancement of our services. We kindly request that you take a moment to provide this information. Your participation is highly valuable to us. You can update your selections in your profile at any time.

Thank you for your support.

Nationality ●

Prefer not to say ▾

Gender ●

Prefer not to say ▾

Age range ●

Prefer not to say ▾

Learning difficulties ●

Prefer not to say ▾

Educational level ●

Prefer not to say ▾

Employment status ●

Prefer not to say ▾

Employment sector ●

Prefer not to say ▾

Security question ●

I'm not a robot

[Create my new account](#) [Cancel](#)

● Required

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Figura 16: Modulo di registrazione della piattaforma

3. Corsi

La piattaforma PreMETS offre due corsi principali (figura 4): **Train-the-Trainer - TN** e **Manutenzione Predittiva - WN**. Ciascun corso è suddiviso in diverse sezioni, ognuna delle quali approfondisce aspetti specifici del tema trattato.

Available courses

TN: Train-the-Trainer 🔑

Teacher: PreMETS Administrator

WN: Predictive Maintenance ➡]

Teacher: PreMETS Administrator

Figura 17: Corsi disponibili sulla piattaforma

TN: Train the Trainer

Questo corso è pensato per supportare i formatori nello sviluppo di strategie efficaci per l'erogazione della formazione e per promuovere il coinvolgimento degli studenti. È suddiviso in 8 sezioni, ognuna delle quali affronta un aspetto specifico dell'insegnamento e dell'apprendimento (figura 5):

- TN1: Strategie per la soddisfazione, la motivazione, il coinvolgimento e le performance degli studenti
- TN2: Riduzione del tasso di abbandono nella formazione online
- TN3: Strategie inclusive e personalizzate per la didattica online nell'istruzione superiore e nella formazione professionale
- TN4: Plasticità cerebrale e connessioni dell'apprendimento
- TN5: Risorse educative aperte, qualitative ed efficaci
- TN6: Linee guida etiche per i learner analytics nel campo della manutenzione predittiva
- TN7: Sistemi di microcredenziali e certificazione delle competenze
- TN8: (Ri)utilizzo delle infrastrutture e delle risorse formative esistenti

WN: Manutenzione Predittiva

Questo corso è incentrato sugli aspetti tecnici e strategici della manutenzione predittiva ed è rivolto ai professionisti dei settori tecnici (figura 6). È articolato in **6 sezioni**:

- **WN1**: Competenze olistiche per la manutenzione predittiva
- **WN2**: Competenze digitali per la manutenzione predittiva
- **WN3**: Competenze green per la manutenzione predittiva
- **WN4**: Competenze per la resilienza nella manutenzione predittiva
- **WN5**: Competenze per l'innovazione e l'imprenditorialità
- **WN6**: Reimparare ad apprendere in un ambiente digitale

PreMETS Home Dashboard My courses Site administration PA Edit mode

TN: Train-the-Trainer

Course Settings Participants Grades Reports More

- General
Announcements
Forum
License
- TN1: Learner happiness, moti...
 - TN1: Video Lecture
 - TN1: Material
 - TN1: Practise Quiz
 - TN1: Final Quiz
 - TN1: "Learner happiness, m..."
- TN2: Reducing the percentag...
 - TN2: Video Lecture
 - TN2: Material
 - TN2: Practise Quiz
 - TN2: Final Quiz

General

Announcements

Forum

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TN1: Learner happiness, motivation, engagement and performance strategies

Activities: 5 Progress: 0 / 4

TN2: Reducing the percentage of drop-outs from online education

Activities: 5 Progress: 0 / 4

TN3: Inclusive and Personalized Education in Predictive Maintenance Strategies for Online Deliveries in Higher and Vocational Education and Beyond

Activities: 5 Progress: 0 / 4

TN4: Brain Plasticity and Learning Connections

Activities: 5 Progress: 0 / 4

TN5: Qualitative & effective open educational resources

Activities: 6 Progress: 0 / 5

TN6: Ethical learner analytics guidelines for preventive maintenance field

Activities: 6 Progress: 0 / 5

TN7: Microcredential systems and skill certification

Activities: 6 Progress: 0 / 5

TN8: (Re)use existing infrastructures and learning resources

Activities: 6 Progress: 0 / 5

Course Completion

Activities: 2 Progress: 0 / 1

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Figura 18: Corso TN e le sue sezioni

The screenshot shows the PreMETS platform interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Home', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Site administration'. The course title 'WN: Predictive Maintenance' is displayed prominently. Below the title, there are tabs for 'Course', 'Settings', 'Participants', 'Grades', 'Reports', and 'More'. The main content area is divided into sections, each with a title, a progress indicator (Activities and Progress), and a right-pointing arrow. The sections are: General, WN1: Holistic PM competences, WN2: Digital skills competences for PM, WN3: Green skills competences for PM, WN4: Resilience competences for PM, WN5: Innovation & entrepreneurship competences, WN6: Relearning how to learn in a digital environment, and Completion. A sidebar on the left contains a menu with 'General', 'WN1: Holistic PM competences', 'WN2: Digital skills competences...', and 'WN2: Final Quiz'.

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Figura 19: Corsi WN e le sue sezioni

Ogni sezione del corso include (Figura 7):

- Video-lezioni: Ogni sezione contiene un video che spiega i concetti chiave. In alcuni casi, i video presentano un formatore che illustra direttamente i contenuti.
- Materiali del corso (figura 8): Ogni sezione è accompagnata da materiali scaricabili, come opuscoli, slide, storyboard e webquest, disponibili in tutte le lingue supportate.
- Quiz: Ogni sezione prevede due tipologie di quiz:
 - Quiz di esercitazione: Composto da 5 domande casuali, fornisce un feedback immediato dopo l'invio. Il punteggio non viene registrato.
 - Quiz finale: Composto da 10 domande casuali tratte dai contenuti della sezione. Non viene fornito feedback; l'utente deve ottenere un punteggio minimo per poter proseguire. Questo quiz è necessario per completare il corso.
- Certificazione: Al termine del percorso di apprendimento e dopo aver superato il quiz finale, l'utente riceve un certificato di completamento relativo a quella sezione.

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Figure 20: Attività della sezione TN6

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Materials listed in the folder:

- Deutsch
 - TN1-Booklet-de.pdf
 - TN1-Slides-de.pdf
 - TN1-Storyboard-de.pdf
 - TN1-WebQuest-de.pdf
- English
 - TN1-Booklet-en.pdf
 - TN1-Slides-en.pdf
 - TN1-Storyboard-en.pdf
 - TN1-WebQuest-en.pdf
- Italiano
 - TN1-Booklet-it.pdf
 - TN1-Slides-it.pdf
 - TN1-Storyboard-it.pdf
 - TN1-WebQuest-it.pdf
- Nederlands
 - TN1-Booklet-nl.pdf
 - TN1-Slides-nl.pdf
 - TN1-Storyboard-nl.pdf
 - TN1-WebQuest-nl.pdf
- Română
 - TN1-Booklet-ro.pdf
 - TN1-Slides-ro.pdf
 - TN1-Storyboard-ro.pdf
 - TN1-WebQuest-ro.pdf
- Srpski
 - TN1-Booklet-sr.pdf
 - TN1-Slides-sr.pdf
 - TN1-Storyboard-sr.pdf
 - TN1-WebQuest-sr.pdf
- Ελληνικά
 - TN1-Booklet-el.pdf
 - TN1-Slides-el.pdf
 - TN1-Storyboard-el.pdf
 - TN1-WebQuest-el.pdf
- TN-Videos.pdf

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National Institute of Transport

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Figura 21: Cartella materiali TN1

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Una volta completate tutte le sezioni del corso TN o WN, gli utenti sbloccheranno una nuova sezione contenente un quiz finale complessivo. Questo quiz include 25 domande casuali, selezionate da tutte le sezioni del corso. Il superamento del quiz finale è necessario per ottenere la certificazione finale del corso.

Dopo aver superato il quiz finale, i partecipanti riceveranno un certificato contenente: nome e cognome, nome del corso, titolo della sezione (se applicabile), data di rilascio, codice di verifica e un QR code. Il codice QR

consente di verificare facilmente l'autenticità del certificato tramite dispositivi mobili. Tutti i certificati possono essere validati direttamente attraverso la piattaforma PreMETS (figura 9).

Figura 22: Esempio di certificazione

I corsi presenti sulla piattaforma PreMETS includono una **bacheca degli annunci** (figura 10) e un **forum di discussione** (figura 11). La bacheca degli annunci consente ai formatori o agli amministratori della piattaforma di condividere aggiornamenti importanti, notifiche e comunicazioni relative al corso con gli utenti. Il forum di discussione offre invece uno spazio interattivo in cui gli studenti possono comunicare con altri partecipanti e con i formatori, porre domande, scambiarsi idee e partecipare a un apprendimento collaborativo.

Figura 23: Annunci dei Corsi TN

The screenshot displays the PreMETS platform interface. At the top, the navigation bar includes 'Home', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Site administration'. The user profile shows 'PA' and an 'Edit mode' toggle. A left sidebar menu lists various course sections, with 'Forum' highlighted. The main content area shows a forum thread titled 'Questions for TN1 - TN4' with a sub-header 'Forum'. Below this, there are navigation options: 'Forum', 'Settings', 'Advanced grading', 'Subscriptions', 'Reports', and 'More'. The thread itself is titled 'Questions for TN1 - TN4' and is posted by 'Afroditi Anagnostopoulou' on Tuesday, 15 October 2024, at 3:09 PM. The message content reads: 'Should you have any questions or require further information, please let us know!'. Action links for 'Permalink', 'Edit', 'Delete', and 'Reply' are visible. At the bottom of the page, there are logos for the European Union (Co-funded by the European Union), CERTH (Centre for Research & Technology Hellas), and CERTH/HT (Hellenic Institute of Transport). A small text block at the bottom states: 'The PreMETS Project has received funding from ERASMUS2027 programme, ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PI-ALL-INNO call, under grant agreement No. 101108469. The PreMETS Platform was developed and is maintained by the CERTH/HT'.

Figura 24: Forum del Corso TN

4. Piattaforma

La piattaforma PreMETS offre una serie di funzionalità progettate per supportare sia l'apprendimento sia l'interazione tra gli utenti:

Ogni utente registrato dispone di una pagina profilo personalizzata (figura 12), nella quale può:

- Visualizzare e modificare le proprie informazioni personali (come nome, indirizzo email, ecc.).
- Scaricare i certificati relativi ai corsi completati.
- Richiedere tutti i dati raccolti dalla piattaforma in relazione alla propria attività.
- Cancellare i dati personali: gli utenti possono scegliere di eliminare il proprio account e tutti i dati associati; tuttavia, questa operazione comporta anche la perdita della possibilità di verificare le certificazioni ottenute.

The screenshot displays the user profile page for a PreMETS Administrator. The page is titled "PA PreMETS Administrator" and includes a "Reset page to default" button. The profile information is organized into several sections:

- User details:** Includes an email address (support@premets-platform.eu), country of residence (Greece), city/town (Piraeus), timezone (Europe/Athens), country (GR), nationality (Greek), gender (Male), age range (25-34), learning difficulties (None), educational level (Doctorate or higher), employment status (Employed full-time), and employment sector (Information Technology). There is an "Edit profile" link.
- Miscellaneous:** Includes links for Notes, My certificates, Forum posts, Forum discussions, and Learning plans.
- Reports:** Includes links for Today's logs, All logs, Outline report, Complete report, Browser sessions, Grades overview, and Grades.
- Login activity:** Shows the first access to the site (Friday, 19 July 2024, 3:27 PM) and the last access to the site (Monday, 17 March 2025, 1:22 PM). It also displays the last IP address (172.71.144.35).
- Mobile app:** Includes a QR code for mobile app access and a note that QR code login is not allowed for site administrators. It also shows the last access to the site (Friday, 8 November 2024, 8:03 AM).
- Privacy and policies:** Includes links for Contact the privacy officer, Data requests, Export all of my personal data, and Policies and agreements.
- Course details:** Includes links for Course profiles, TN: Train-the-Trainer, and WN: Predictive Maintenance.

Figura 25: Esempio di pagina del profilo dell'utente con opzioni e informazioni

La piattaforma include una **bacheca globale degli annunci** in cui gli utenti possono visualizzare aggiornamenti e notifiche importanti pubblicate dagli amministratori della piattaforma o dai formatori dei corsi. Questa funzionalità aiuta a mantenere gli utenti informati su nuovi contenuti, eventi in programma o notizie relative alla piattaforma.

Calendario degli Eventi

Il calendario mostra tutti gli eventi rilevanti, come scadenze dei corsi, webinar e interventi di manutenzione della piattaforma (figura 13). Gli utenti possono consultare questo calendario per rimanere aggiornati sulle date importanti.

Figura 26: Esempio di evento nel calendario, “WN - Pre-Pilota Timisoara Giorno 3”

Accessibilità e Supporto Multilingue

PreMETS è progettata per essere accessibile, con strumenti e funzionalità verificate tramite audit esterni sull’accessibilità. La piattaforma supporta un’ampia gamma di esigenze, inclusa la compatibilità con lettori di schermo e opzioni di navigazione alternative.

Inoltre, gli utenti possono selezionare la propria lingua preferita attraverso il menu linguistico della piattaforma. Sebbene l’inglese sia pienamente supportato, una parte significativa dei contenuti è tradotta in altre lingue, rendendo la piattaforma accessibile a utenti provenienti da contesti linguistici differenti.

La piattaforma è regolata da tre principali policy: i Termini di Utilizzo, la Cookie Policy e la Privacy Policy.

- **Termini di Utilizzo:** definiscono le regole e le linee guida che gli utenti devono rispettare durante l’accesso e l’utilizzo della piattaforma. Il documento stabilisce le responsabilità sia della piattaforma che dell’utente, includendo comportamenti accettabili, limitazioni d’uso e conseguenze in caso di violazione. Affronta inoltre aspetti legali come i diritti di proprietà intellettuale, le clausole di esclusione di responsabilità e le limitazioni di responsabilità, configurandosi essenzialmente come un accordo tra l’utente e la piattaforma sull’utilizzo del servizio
- **Cookie Policy:** spiega come la piattaforma utilizza i cookie per migliorare l’esperienza dell’utente. I cookie sono piccoli file di testo salvati sul dispositivo dell’utente che aiutano la piattaforma a ricordare informazioni come le preferenze, i dati di accesso o a tracciare il modo in cui il sito viene utilizzato. La policy descrive i tipi di cookie utilizzati, le finalità del loro utilizzo (ad esempio per funzionalità o marketing) e fornisce istruzioni su come gestire o disattivare i cookie tramite le impostazioni del browser.
- **Privacy Policy:** descrive le modalità con cui la piattaforma raccoglie, conserva e protegge i dati personali degli utenti. Spiega quali tipi di informazioni vengono raccolti—come nomi, indirizzi email o dati di pagamento—e come tali informazioni vengono utilizzate, ad esempio per migliorare i servizi o le comunicazioni. La policy chiarisce anche se e come i dati possano essere condivisi con terze parti e informa gli utenti sui propri diritti di accesso, aggiornamento o cancellazione dei dati personali.

Tutte le policy sono elencate al seguente link: <https://premets-platform.eu/admin/tool/policy/viewall.php>

5. Conclusioni

La piattaforma PreMETS è un ambiente completo e intuitivo che offre una formazione di alta qualità nell'ambito della manutenzione predittiva. Grazie a un'interfaccia user-friendly, a risorse didattiche diversificate e a numerose funzionalità interattive, PreMETS consente agli utenti di sviluppare competenze fondamentali in un contesto collaborativo e coinvolgente.

Seguendo questo manuale, gli utenti possono navigare facilmente nella piattaforma, accedere ai corsi, completare i quiz e ottenere certificazioni di valore al termine della formazione. Che si tratti di studenti, formatori o amministratori di piattaforma, PreMETS mette a disposizione tutti gli strumenti necessari per un'esperienza educativa efficace e di successo.

Dutch Version

1. Inleiding

Het PreMETS platform is een innovatieve onderwijsomgeving gebouwd op Moodle, een open-source Learning Management System (LMS). Het biedt gespecialiseerde training op twee belangrijke gebieden: TN: Train-the-Trainer en WN: Voorspellend Onderhoud. Het platform is ontworpen om zowel technische expertise als instructieontwikkeling te ondersteunen, door leerlingen interactieve en boeiende educatieve content te bieden. Door middel van een verscheidenheid aan activiteiten, waaronder quizzen, instructievideo's en discussieforums, krijgen gebruikers toegang tot waardevolle bronnen die zijn afgestemd op hun individuele leerbehoeften.

PreMETS is wereldwijd toegankelijk via een Content Delivery Network (CDN), wat zorgt voor snelle en betrouwbare toegang in verschillende regio's, en het wordt gehost bij Microsoft Azure cloud computing. Het platform is meertalig en ondersteunt de volgende talen: Engels, Duits, Italiaans, Nederlands, Roemeens, Servisch en Grieks. Het platform is toegankelijk op <https://premets-platform.eu> (Afbeelding 1).

Om de leerervaring te verbeteren, maakt PreMETS gebruik van adaptieve leermethoden, zodat gebruikers in hun eigen tempo vorderingen kunnen maken op basis van hun kennisniveau en prestaties. Door gebruik te maken van gegevensanalyses en feedback van gebruikers, verfijnt het platform voortdurend de inhoud en de methoden om de betrokkenheid en het kennisbehoud te optimaliseren. Deze gepersonaliseerde aanpak zorgt ervoor dat zowel trainers als technische professionals gerichte en effectieve instructies krijgen die zijn afgestemd op hun specifieke behoeften.

PreMETS: Predictive Maintenance Education and Training System

Welcome to the **PreMETS: Predictive Maintenance Education and Training System**. PreMETS is an alliance for boosting the European innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education and training. In PreMETS, collaboration and knowledge sharing are crucial to promote connectivity, inclusivity, innovation, and equal access to high-quality education in Predictive Maintenance.

Predictive Maintenance (PM) is crucial for optimizing economic resources and fundamental infrastructure systems. Its primary function is to foresee and prevent critical infrastructure breakdowns or failures through digital approaches.

This digital education platform contains two educational programs:

1. the **WN: Predictive Maintenance** which integrates both higher education and vocational education standards and
2. the **TN: Train-the-Trainer** for academic, vocational, and corporate levels, enhancing accessibility and effectiveness of PM education.

These courses offer a micro-credential certificate, offering recognition and certification for PM skills for both learners and trainers.

Available courses

TN: Train-the-Trainer

Teacher: PreMETS Administrator

WN: Predictive Maintenance

Teacher: PreMETS Administrator

Site announcements

There are no discussion topics yet in this forum

Upcoming events

There are no upcoming events
[Go to calendar...](#)

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Afbeelding 1: Startpagina van het platform

2. Registratie

Om toegang te krijgen tot de cursussen en inhoud op het PreMETS platform is gebruikersregistratie vereist (afbeelding 2). Registratie is eenvoudig en kan worden voltooid via e-mail of door u aan te melden met een Google- of Microsoft-account (afbeelding 3).

Afbeelding 2: Inlogpagina van het platform

Stappen voor registratie:

1. Accepteer het beleid van het platform: Bekijk en accepteer tijdens de registratie de Gebruiksvoorwaarden van het platform, Cookies Beleid en Privacybeleid is vereist.
2. Vul verplichte velden in: Het registratieformulier vraagt om essentiële informatie zoals voor- en achternaam, land, gebruikersnaam, e-mailadres en een wachtwoord.

Gebruikers krijgen daarnaast de mogelijkheid om een demografische vragenlijst in te vullen, met velden voor:

- Nationaliteit
- Geslacht
- Leeftijd
- Leerproblemen
- Opleidingsniveau
- Werkstatus
- Sector werkgelegenheid

Zodra de registratie is voltooid en het e-mailadres is geverifieerd, krijgen gebruikers toegang tot alle functies en inhoud van het platform. Dit omvat het inschrijven voor cursussen, deelnemen aan discussies en het maken van toetsen.

New account

Username ❗

The password must have at least 8 characters, at least 1 digit(s), at least 1 lower case letter(s), at least 1 upper case letter(s), at least 1 special character(s) such as *, -, , or #

Password ❗

Email address ❗

Email (again) ❗

First name ❗

Last name ❗

City/town

Country of residence ❗

Select a country ⌵

Demographic Information

The demographic fields provided below are intended exclusively for analytics and research purposes. We assure you that all information submitted will be treated with the utmost confidentiality and will be accessible solely to you. Neither your instructors nor any other users will have access to this data.

By completing these fields, you will significantly contribute to the enhancement of our services. We kindly request that you take a moment to provide this information. Your participation is highly valuable to us. You can update your selections in your profile at any time.

Thank you for your support.

Nationality ❗

Prefer not to say ⌵

Gender ❗

Prefer not to say ⌵

Age range ❗

Prefer not to say ⌵

Learning difficulties ❗

Prefer not to say ⌵

Educational level ❗

Prefer not to say ⌵

Employment status ❗

Prefer not to say ⌵

Employment sector ❗

Prefer not to say ⌵

Security question ✔

I'm not a robot reCAPTCHA
Privacy - Terms

[Create my new account](#) [Cancel](#)

❗ Required

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Afbeelding 3: Registratieformulier van het platform

3. Cursussen

Het PreMETS-platform biedt twee primaire cursussen (afbeelding 4): Train-de-trainer - TN en Voorspellend Onderhoud - WN. Elke cursus is onderverdeeld in verschillende secties die zich richten op verschillende aspecten van het onderwerp.

Available courses

TN: Train-the-Trainer

Teacher: PreMETS Administrator

WN: Predictive Maintenance

Teacher: PreMETS Administrator

Afbeelding 4: Beschikbare cursussen op het platform

TN: Train-de-trainer

Deze cursus is ontworpen om docenten te helpen effectieve strategieën te ontwikkelen voor het geven van trainingen en het bevorderen van de betrokkenheid van leerlingen. Hij is onderverdeeld in 8 secties, die elk een ander element van lesgeven en leren behandelen (Afbeelding 5).

- TN1: Geluk, motivatie, betrokkenheid en prestatiestrategieën van leerlingen
- TN2: Het percentage drop-outs in online onderwijs verlagen
- TN3: Inclusieve en gepersonaliseerde onderwijsstrategieën voor online leveringen in het hoger en beroepsonderwijs
- TN4: Hersenplasticiteit en leerverbindingen
- TN5: Kwalitatieve en effectieve open leermiddelen
- TN6: Richtlijnen voor ethische leeranalyse op het gebied van preventief onderhoud
- TN7: Microcredentialsystemen en vaardigheidscertificering
- TN8: (Her)gebruik van bestaande infrastructuren en leermiddelen

WN: Voorspellend Onderhoud

Deze cursus richt zich op de technische en strategische elementen van voorspellend onderhoud en is bedoeld voor professionals die werkzaam zijn in technische vakgebieden (Afbeelding 6). De cursus bestaat uit 6 delen:

- WN1: Holistische competenties voor voorspellend onderhoud
- WN2: Digitale vaardigheden voor voorspellend onderhoud
- WN3: Groene vaardigheden competenties voor predictief onderhoud
- WN4: Veerkrachtcompetenties voor voorspellend onderhoud
- WN5: Innovatie en ondernemerscompetenties
- WN6: Opnieuw leren in een digitale omgeving

PreMETS Home Dashboard My courses Site administration PA Edit mode

TN: Train-the-Trainer

Course Settings Participants Grades Reports More

- General
 - Announcements
 - Forum
 - License
- TN1: Learner happiness, moti...
 - TN1: Video Lecture
 - TN1: Material
 - TN1: Practise Quiz
 - TN1: Final Quiz
 - TN1: "Learner happiness, m..."
- TN2: Reducing the percentag...
 - TN2: Video Lecture
 - TN2: Material
 - TN2: Practise Quiz
 - TN2: Final Quiz

General

Announcements

Forum

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TN1: Learner happiness, motivation, engagement and performance strategies

Activities: 5 Progress: 0 / 4

TN2: Reducing the percentage of drop-outs from online education

Activities: 5 Progress: 0 / 4

TN3: Inclusive and Personalized Education in Predictive Maintenance Strategies for Online Deliveries in Higher and Vocational Education and Beyond

Activities: 5 Progress: 0 / 4

TN4: Brain Plasticity and Learning Connections

Activities: 5 Progress: 0 / 4

TN5: Qualitative & effective open educational resources

Activities: 6 Progress: 0 / 5

TN6: Ethical learner analytics guidelines for preventive maintenance field

Activities: 6 Progress: 0 / 5

TN7: Microcredential systems and skill certification

Activities: 6 Progress: 0 / 5

TN8: (Re)use existing infrastructures and learning resources

Activities: 6 Progress: 0 / 5

Course Completion

Activities: 2 Progress: 0 / 1

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Afbeelding 5: TN-cursus en zijn secties

The screenshot shows the PreMETS course interface for 'WN: Predictive Maintenance'. The top navigation bar includes 'Home', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Site administration'. The course title 'WN: Predictive Maintenance' is prominently displayed. Below the title, there are tabs for 'Course', 'Settings', 'Participants', 'Grades', 'Reports', and 'More'. The main content area is divided into several sections, each with a title and progress indicator:

- General**: Includes 'Announcements' and 'Forum'. A note states: 'PreMETS materials are licensed under Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0 International'.
- WN1: Holistic PM competences**: Progress: 0 / 4
- WN2: Digital skills competences for PM**: Progress: 0 / 4
- WN3: Green skills competences for PM**: Progress: 0 / 4
- WN4: Resilience competences for PM**: Progress: 0 / 4
- WN5: Innovation & entrepreneurship competences**: Progress: 0 / 4
- WN6: Relearning how to learn in a digital environment**: Progress: 0 / 4
- Completion**: Progress: 0 / 1

At the bottom of the page, there are logos for the European Union, CERTH (Centre for Research & Technology Hellas), and CERTH/HT (Institute of Transport). Text below the logos states: 'The PreMETS Project has received funding from ERASMUS2027 programme, ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PI-ALL-INNO call, under grant agreement No. 101108469. The PreMETS Platform was developed and is maintained by the CERTH/HT'.

Afbeelding 6: WN-cursus en secties

Elke delen bevat (Afbeelding 7):

- Videocolleges: Elke sectie bevat een video waarin de belangrijkste concepten worden uitgelegd. In sommige gevallen wordt het materiaal in de video's gepresenteerd door een instructeur
- Cursusmateriaal (afbeelding 8): Bij elk onderdeel hoort downloadbaar lesboekjes, dia's, storyboards en webquests, beschikbaar in alle ondersteunde talen
- Quizen: Elke sectie heeft twee soorten quizen:
 - Oefenquiz: Bevat 5 willekeurige vragen, waarbij leerlingen direct na het insturen feedback krijgen. Er wordt geen score geregistreerd voor de oefenquiz

- Eindquiz: Bevat 10 willekeurige vragen uit de sectie-inhoud. Er wordt geen feedback gegeven en leerlingen moeten een voldoende halen om verder te gaan. Deze test is noodzakelijk om de cursus te voltooien
- Certificering: Na het leerproces en het slagen voor de laatste quiz, krijgen gebruikers een certificaat van voltooiing voor die sectie.

The screenshot displays the PreMETS user interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'PreMETS', 'Home', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Site administration'. On the right, there are user profile icons and a language dropdown set to 'PA', along with an 'Edit mode' toggle. A left-hand sidebar shows a course tree with 'TN6: Ethical learner analytics...' selected. The main content area is titled 'TN / TN6: Ethical learner analytics guidelines for preventive maintenance field'. Below this, the section 'TN6: Ethical learner analytics guidelines for preventive maintenance field' is shown with a 'Mark as done' button. The first activity is 'Video Lecture with Instructor', featuring a PreMETS logo and a graphic with the text 'PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM'. Below this is a 'Video Lecture' player with a play button. A list of activities follows: 'TN6: Material' (Mark as done), 'TN6: Practise Quiz' (To do), 'TN6: Final Quiz' (To do), and 'TN6: "Ethical learner analytics guidelines for preventive maintenance field" Certificate' (To do). Each activity has a lock icon and a 'Not available unless...' message.

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Afbeelding 7: TN6 sectie activiteiten

The screenshot displays the PreMETS user interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Home', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Site administration'. A user profile 'PA' and an 'Edit mode' toggle are also visible. A left-hand sidebar contains a menu with categories like 'General', 'TN1: Learner happiness, moti...', and 'TN2: Reducing the percentag...'. The main content area shows the breadcrumb 'TN / TN1: Learner happiness, motivation, engagement and performance strategies / TN1: Material'. Below this, the 'TN1: Material' folder is selected, showing a list of files organized by language: Deutsch, English, Italiano, Nederlands, Română, Srpski, and Ελληνικά. Each language folder contains sub-items for 'Booklet', 'Slides', 'Storyboard', and 'WebQuest'. A 'Download folder' button is present at the top right of the file list.

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Afbeelding 8: TN1 materia folder

Alle materialen van het PreMETS platform zijn gelicenseerd onder de Creative Commons Naamsvermelding-

NietCommercieel-GeenAfgeleideWerken 4.0 Internationale Licentie, waardoor gebruikers de inhoud vrij kunnen openen en delen met de juiste naamsvermelding, maar niet voor commerciële doeleinden, en zonder de mogelijkheid om de materialen te wijzigen.

Na het voltooien van alle secties in de TN of WN cursus, zullen gebruikers een nieuwe sectie ontgrendelen die een uitgebreide eindquiz bevat. Deze laatste test bevat 25 willekeurige vragen uit alle secties van de cursus. Als de cursist de laatste test met succes afrondt, ontvangt hij het eindcertificaat van de cursus.

Nadat ze geslaagd zijn voor de laatste test, ontvangen de leerlingen een certificaat met hun volledige naam, de naam van de cursus, de titel van de sectie (indien van toepassing), de naam van de cursus, de afgiftedatum, een verificatiecode en een QR-code. Met de QR-code kunnen certificaten eenvoudig worden geverifieerd met mobiele apparaten (afbeelding 9).

Afbeelding 9: Voorbeeld van certificering

Cursussen op het PreMETS-platform bevatten een mededelingenbord (afbeelding 10) en een discussieforum (afbeelding 11). Op het mededelingenbord kunnen docenten of platformbeheerders belangrijke updates, kennisgevingen en cursusgerelateerd nieuws met gebruikers delen. Het discussieforum biedt een interactieve ruimte waar studenten kunnen communiceren met andere studenten en docenten, vragen kunnen stellen, ideeën kunnen uitwisselen en samen kunnen leren.

PreMETS Home Dashboard My courses Site administration PA Edit mode

General

- Announcements
- Forum
- License

TN1: Learner happiness, moti...

- TN1: Video Lecture
- TN1: Material
- TN1: Practise Quiz
- TN1: Final Quiz

TN1: "Learner happiness, m...

TN2: Reducing the percentag...

- TN2: Video Lecture
- TN2: Material
- TN2: Practise Quiz
- TN2: Final Quiz

TN / General / Announcements

Announcements

Forum Settings Advanced grading Subscriptions Reports More

General news and announcements

Search forums Add discussion topic

Discussion	Started by	Last post ↓	Replies
☆ PreMETS Certification	Afroditi Anagno... 17 Oct 2024	Afroditi Anagno... 17 Oct 2024	0
☆ Train-the-Trainers Pre-Pilot 14-18/10/2024	Afroditi Anagno... 15 Oct 2024	Afroditi Anagno... 15 Oct 2024	0

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Afbeelding 10: TN-cursusaankondigen

PreMETS Home Dashboard My courses Site administration PA Edit mode

General

- Announcements
- Forum
- License

TN1: Learner happiness, moti...

- TN1: Video Lecture
- TN1: Material
- TN1: Practise Quiz
- TN1: Final Quiz

TN1: "Learner happiness, m...

TN2: Reducing the percentag...

- TN2: Video Lecture
- TN2: Material
- TN2: Practise Quiz
- TN2: Final Quiz

TN / General / Forum / Questions for TN1 - TN4

Forum

Forum Settings Advanced grading Subscriptions Reports More

Questions for TN1 - TN4

Questions for TN5-TN8

Display replies in nested form Move this discussion to ... Move Settings

Questions for TN1 - TN4
by Afroditi Anagnostopoulou - Tuesday, 15 October 2024, 3:09 PM

Should you have any questions or require further information, please let us know!

Permalink Edit Delete Reply

Questions for TN5-TN8

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Afbeelding 11: TN-cursusforum

4. Platform

Het PreMETS platform biedt een reeks functies die ontworpen zijn om zowel het leren als de interactie met de gebruiker te ondersteunen.

Elke gebruiker beschikt over een persoonlijk profiel waar (Afbeelding 12):

- Persoonlijke gegevens kunnen worden ingezien en bewerkt
- Certificaten kunnen worden gedownload
- Gegevens die het platform verzamelt kunnen worden opgevraagd
- Het account en bijbehorende gegevens verwijderd kunnen worden (verificatie van certificaten is dan niet meer mogelijk)

The screenshot displays the 'PreMETS Administrator' profile page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'PreMETS', 'Home', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Site administration'. A user profile icon 'PA' and 'Edit mode' toggle are also visible. A 'Reset page to default' button is located at the top right of the profile area.

The profile is titled 'PA PreMETS Administrator' and is divided into several sections:

- User details:** Includes 'Email address' (support@premets-platform.eu), 'Country of residence' (Greece), 'City/town' (Piraeus), 'Timezone' (Europe/Athens), 'Country' (GR), 'Nationality' (Greek), 'Gender' (Male), 'Age range' (25-34), 'Learning difficulties' (None), 'Educational level' (Doctorate or higher), 'Employment status' (Employed full-time), and 'Employment sector' (Information Technology). An 'Edit profile' link is present.
- Miscellaneous:** Contains links for 'Notes', 'My certificates', 'Forum posts', 'Forum discussions', and 'Learning plans'.
- Reports:** Contains links for 'Today's logs', 'All logs', 'Outline report', 'Complete report', 'Browser sessions', 'Grades overview', and 'Grades'.
- Login activity:** Shows 'First access to site' (Friday, 19 July 2024, 3:27 PM) and 'Last access to site' (Monday, 17 March 2025, 1:22 PM). It also lists the 'Last IP address' as 172.71.144.35.
- Mobile app:** Includes a 'QR code for mobile app access' and a warning: 'For security reasons login via QR code is not allowed for site administrators or if you are logged in as another user.' It also shows the 'Last access to site' (Friday, 8 November 2024, 8:03 AM).
- Privacy and policies:** Contains links for 'Contact the privacy officer', 'Data requests', 'Export all of my personal data', and 'Policies and agreements'.
- Course details:** Lists 'Course profiles' such as 'TN: Train-the-Trainer' and 'WN: Predictive Maintenance'.

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Afbeelding 12: Voorbeeld profielpagina met opties en informatie voor de gebruiker

Wereldwijd mededelingenbord

Het platform heeft een globaal mededelingenbord waar gebruikers updates en belangrijke meldingen kunnen bekijken die door platformbeheerders of cursusdocenten geplaatst zijn. Deze functie helpt gebruikers op de hoogte te blijven van nieuwe inhoud, komende evenementen of platform-gerelateerd nieuws.

Kalender

De kalender toont alle relevante gebeurtenissen, zoals komende deadlines voor cursussen, webinars en onderhoudsschema's voor het systeem (afbeelding 13). Gebruikers kunnen deze kalender gebruiken om op de hoogte te blijven van belangrijke data.

Afbeelding 13: Voorbeeld kalenderegebeurtenis, "WN - Pre-Pilot Timisoara Dag 3"

Toegankelijkheid en meertalige ondersteuning

PreMETS is ontworpen om toegankelijk te zijn, met tools en functies die zijn geverifieerd door externe toegankelijkheidsaudits. Het platform ondersteunt een breed scala aan toegankelijkheidsbehoeften, waaronder schermlezers en alternatieve navigatieopties.

Bovendien kunnen gebruikers hun voorkeurstaal selecteren via het taalmenu van het platform. Hoewel Engels volledig wordt ondersteund, is een aanzienlijk deel van de inhoud van het platform vertaald naar andere talen. Dit zorgt ervoor dat het platform toegankelijk is voor gebruikers met verschillende taalachtergronden.

Voor het platform gelden drie belangrijke beleidsregels:

- **In de Gebruiksvoorwaarden** worden de regels en richtlijnen beschreven waaraan gebruikers zich moeten houden bij het betreden of gebruiken van het platform. Het behandelt de verantwoordelijkheden van zowel het platform als de gebruiker, inclusief aanvaardbaar gedrag, gebruiksbepalingen en consequenties voor het schenden van deze voorwaarden. Het behandelt ook juridische overwegingen zoals intellectuele eigendomsrechten, disclaimers en aansprakelijkheidsbepalingen, en dient in wezen als een overeenkomst tussen de gebruiker en het platform over hoe de service kan worden gebruikt.
- **Het Cookiebeleid** legt uit hoe het platform cookies gebruikt om de gebruikerservaring te verbeteren. Cookies zijn kleine tekstbestanden die worden opgeslagen op het apparaat van een gebruiker en die het platform helpen bepaalde details te onthouden, zoals voorkeuren, inloggegevens of bijhouden hoe de site wordt gebruikt. Dit beleid beschrijft de soorten cookies die worden gebruikt, de redenen voor het gebruik ervan (zoals voor functionaliteit of marketing) en geeft instructies voor gebruikers over hoe ze cookies kunnen beheren of uitschakelen in hun browserinstellingen.
- **Het Privacybeleid** beschrijft hoe het platform persoonlijke gegevens van gebruikers verzamelt, opslaat en beschermt. Er wordt uitgelegd welke soorten persoonlijke informatie worden verzameld, zoals namen, e-mailadressen of betalingsgegevens, en hoe die informatie wordt gebruikt, hetzij voor het verbeteren van diensten of communicatie. Het beleid gaat ook in op hoe het platform gegevens kan

delen met derden en informeert gebruikers over hun rechten om toegang te krijgen tot hun persoonlijke gegevens, deze bij te werken of te verwijderen.

Alle beleidsregels staan vermeld op de volgende link: <https://premets-platform.eu/admin/tool/policy/viewall.php>

5. Conclusie

Het PreMETS platform is een uitgebreide en gebruiksvriendelijke omgeving die hoogwaardige training biedt in Predictive Maintenance. Met een intuïtieve interface, diverse leermiddelen en een scala aan interactieve functies stelt PreMETS cursisten in staat om essentiële vaardigheden te ontwikkelen in een collaboratieve en boeiende omgeving.

Door deze handleiding te volgen, kunnen gebruikers gemakkelijk door het platform navigeren, cursussen openen, quizen voltooien en waardevolle certificeringen ontvangen na het voltooien van een cursus. Of u nu een cursist, instructeur of platformbeheerder bent, PreMETS biedt alle hulpmiddelen die nodig zijn voor een succesvolle educatieve ervaring.

Romanian Version

1. Introducere

Platforma PreMETS este un mediu educațional inovator, construit pe Moodle, un sistem de management al învățării (LMS) open-source. Aceasta oferă formare specializată în două domenii cheie: **TN: Train-the-Trainer** și **WN: Mentenanță Predictivă**. Platforma este concepută pentru a sprijini atât dezvoltarea expertizei tehnice, cât și a competențelor didactice, oferind cursanților conținut educațional interactiv și captivant. Printr-o varietate de activități – inclusiv chestionare, videoclipuri educaționale și forumuri de discuții – utilizatorii pot accesa resurse valoroase adaptate nevoilor lor individuale de învățare.

PreMETS este accesibilă la nivel global printr-o **rețea de livrare a conținutului (CDN)**, asigurând un acces rapid și fiabil în diferite regiuni, și este găzduită în infrastructura de cloud computing Microsoft Azure. Platforma este **multilingvă**, oferind suport pentru următoarele limbi: **engleză, germană, italiană, neerlandeză, română, sârbă și greacă**. Aceasta poate fi accesată la <https://premets-platform.eu> (figura 1).

Pentru a îmbunătăți experiența de învățare, PreMETS încorporează **metodologii de învățare adaptivă**, permițând utilizatorilor să progreseze în ritmul propriu, în funcție de nivelul de cunoștințe și de performanță. Prin valorificarea **analizei datelor și a feedback-ului utilizatorilor**, platforma își îmbunătățește continuu conținutul și metodele de livrare, optimizând astfel implicarea cursanților și retenția cunoștințelor. Acest **proces personalizat** garantează că atât instructorii, cât și profesioniștii tehnici beneficiază de o instruire țintită și eficientă, adaptată nevoilor lor specifice.

PreMETS: Predictive Maintenance Education and Training System

Welcome to the **PreMETS: Predictive Maintenance Education and Training System**. PreMETS is an alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education and training. In PreMETS, collaboration and knowledge sharing are crucial to promote connectivity, inclusivity, innovation, and equal access to high-quality education in Predictive Maintenance.

Predictive Maintenance (PM) is crucial for optimizing economic resources and fundamental infrastructure systems. Its primary function is to foresee and prevent critical infrastructure breakdowns or failures through digital approaches.

This digital education platform contains two educational programs:

1. the **WN: Predictive Maintenance** which integrates both higher education and vocational education standards and
2. the **TN: Train-the-Trainer** for academic, vocational, and corporate levels, enhancing accessibility and effectiveness of PM education.

These courses offer a micro-credential certificate, offering recognition and certification for PM skills for both learners and trainers.

Available courses

TN: Train-the-Trainer

Teacher: PreMETS Administrator

WN: Predictive Maintenance

Teacher: PreMETS Administrator

Site announcements

There are no discussion topics yet in this forum

Upcoming events

There are no upcoming events
[Go to calendar...](#)

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Figura 1: Pagina de pornire a platformei

2. Înregistrare

Pentru a accesa cursurile și conținutul de pe platforma PreMETS, este necesară înregistrarea utilizatorilor (figura 2). Procesul de înregistrare este simplu și poate fi realizat prin e-mail sau prin autentificare cu un cont Google sau Microsoft (figura 3).

Figura 2: Pagina de conectare a platformei

Pașii de înregistrare:

1. **Acceptarea politicilor platformei** – În timpul înregistrării, utilizatorii trebuie să **revizuiască și să accepte** documentele **Termeni de utilizare, Politica privind cookie-urile și Politica de confidențialitate** ale platformei.
2. **Completarea câmpurilor obligatorii** – Formularul de înregistrare solicită informații esențiale, precum:
 - Nume și prenume
 - Țara de rezidență
 - Nume de utilizator
 - Adresă de e-mail
 - Parolă
3. **(Opțional) Completarea unui sondaj demografic**, care include:
 - Naționalitate
 - Gen
 - Interval de vârstă
 - Dificultăți de învățare
 - Nivel educațional
 - Statut profesional
 - Sectorul de activitate

După finalizarea înregistrării și verificarea adresei de e-mail, utilizatorii vor avea acces la toate funcționalitățile și conținutul platformei. Acest lucru include **înscrierea la cursuri, participarea la discuții și susținerea evaluărilor**.

New account

Username ●

The password must have at least 8 characters, at least 1 digit(s), at least 1 lower case letter(s), at least 1 upper case letter(s), at least 1 special character(s) such as !, -, or #

Password ●

Email address ●

Email (again) ●

First name ●

Last name ●

City/town

Country of residence ●

Select a country ▾

▾ Demographic Information

The demographic fields provided below are intended exclusively for analytics and research purposes. We assure you that all information submitted will be treated with the utmost confidentiality and will be accessible solely to you. Neither your instructors nor any other users will have access to this data.

By completing these fields, you will significantly contribute to the enhancement of our services. We kindly request that you take a moment to provide this information. Your participation is highly valuable to us. You can update your selections in your profile at any time.

Thank you for your support.

Nationality ●

Prefer not to say ▾

Gender ●

Prefer not to say ▾

Age range ●

Prefer not to say ▾

Learning difficulties ●

Prefer not to say ▾

Educational level ●

Prefer not to say ▾

Employment status ●

Prefer not to say ▾

Employment sector ●

Prefer not to say ▾

Security question ?

I'm not a robot

Create my new account Cancel

● Required

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Figura 3: Formularul de înregistrare al platformei

3. Cursuri

Platforma PreMETS oferă două cursuri principale (figura 4): **Train-the-Trainer - TN** și **Mentenanță Predictivă - WN**. Fiecare curs este împărțit în mai multe secțiuni, concentrându-se pe diferite aspecte ale subiectului abordat.

Available courses

TN: Train-the-Trainer 🔑

Teacher: PreMETS Administrator

WN: Predictive Maintenance ➡

Teacher: PreMETS Administrator

Figura 4: Cursuri disponibile pe platformă

TN: Train-the-Trainer

Acest curs este conceput pentru a ajuta educatorii să dezvolte strategii eficiente de predare și să încurajeze implicarea cursanților. Este structurat în **8 secțiuni**, fiecare abordând un aspect esențial al procesului de predare și învățare (figura 5): **TN1**: Fericirea, motivația, implicarea și strategiile de îmbunătățire a performanței cursanților

TN2: Reducerea ratei de abandon în educația online

TN3: Strategii de educație incluzivă și personalizată pentru livrarea online în învățământul superior și vocațional

TN4: Plasticitatea creierului și conexiunile de învățare

TN5: Resurse educaționale deschise, calitative și eficiente

TN6: Ghiduri etice pentru analiza cursanților în domeniul mentenanței predictive

TN7: Sisteme de microcertificare și validare a competențelor

TN8: (Re)utilizarea infrastructurilor existente și a resurselor educaționale

WN: Mentenanță Predictivă

Acest curs este axat pe **elementele tehnice și strategice** ale mentenanței predictive, fiind destinat profesioniștilor din domeniul tehnic (figura 6). Este împărțit în **6 secțiuni**:

WN1: Competențe holistice în mentenanța predictive

WN2: Competențe digitale pentru mentenanța predictivă

WN3: Competențe ecologice pentru mentenanța predictive

WN4: Competențe de reziliență pentru mentenanța predictive

WN5: Competențe de inovare și antreprenoriat

WN6: Reînvățarea procesului de învățare într-un mediu digital

The screenshot displays the PreMETS platform interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'PreMETS', 'Home', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Site administration'. On the right, there are user profile icons and an 'Edit mode' toggle. A sidebar on the left shows a course tree with sections like 'General', 'Announcements', 'Forum', 'License', and several 'TN' (Train-the-Trainer) modules. The main content area is titled 'TN: Train-the-Trainer' and includes sub-tabs for 'Course', 'Settings', 'Participants', 'Grades', 'Reports', and 'More'. Below this, a list of course modules is shown, each with a title, a progress indicator (Activities and Progress), and a right-pointing arrow. The modules are: 'General', 'TN1: Learner happiness, motivation, engagement and performance strategies', 'TN2: Reducing the percentage of drop-outs from online education', 'TN3: Inclusive and Personalized Education in Predictive Maintenance Strategies for Online Deliveries in Higher and Vocational Education and Beyond', 'TN4: Brain Plasticity and Learning Connections', 'TN5: Qualitative & effective open educational resources', 'TN6: Ethical learner analytics guidelines for preventive maintenance field', 'TN7: Microcredential systems and skill certification', 'TN8: (Re)use existing infrastructures and learning resources', and 'Course Completion'. A small question mark icon is visible on the right side of the page.

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Figura 5: Cursul TN și modulele sale

The screenshot shows the PreMETS course interface for 'WN: Predictive Maintenance'. The sidebar on the left lists various course sections under categories like 'General', 'WN1: Holistic PM competences', and 'WN2: Digital skills competences'. The main content area displays a list of course sections with their respective activity counts and progress bars. At the bottom, there are logos for the European Union, CERTH, and CERTHIT, along with funding information from the ERASMUS+2027 programme.

Figura 6: Cursul WN și modulele sale

Structura fiecărei secțiuni de curs (figura 7)

Fiecare secțiune a cursurilor include următoarele elemente:

Lecții video – Fiecare secțiune conține un videoclip care explică conceptele esențiale. În unele cazuri, videoclipurile includ un instructor care prezintă materialul.

Materiale de curs (figura 8) – Fiecare secțiune oferă materiale descărcabile, precum **broșuri, diapozitive, scenariile educaționale și webquest-uri**, disponibile în toate limbile suportate de platformă.

Chestionare – Fiecare secțiune include două tipuri de teste:

Chestionar de practică – Conține **5 întrebări aleatorii**, iar cursanții primesc feedback imediat după trimiterea răspunsurilor. Acest test nu influențează scorul final.

Chestionar final – Include **10 întrebări aleatorii** din conținutul secțiunii. Feedback-ul nu este oferit, iar cursanții trebuie să obțină o notă de trecere pentru a avansa. Acest test este obligatoriu pentru finalizarea cursului.

Certificare – După parcurgerea secțiunii și promovarea chestionarului final, utilizatorii primesc un **certificat de finalizare** pentru acea secțiune.

The screenshot displays the PreMETS user interface. On the left is a navigation menu with a search bar and a list of course items, including 'TN6: Ethical learner analytics...' which is currently selected. The main content area shows the title 'TN6: Ethical learner analytics guidelines for preventive maintenance field'. Below the title is a 'Video Lecture with Instructor' section featuring a video player with a play button and a 'Mark as done' button. The video player shows a slide with the PreMETS logo and the text 'PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM'. Below the video is another 'Video Lecture' section, also with a play button and a 'Mark as done' button. At the bottom, there is a list of activities: 'TN6: Material', 'TN6: Practise Quiz', 'TN6: Final Quiz', and 'TN6: "Ethical learner analytics guidelines for preventive maintenance field" Certificate'. Each activity has a 'Mark as done' button and a status indicator.

Figura 7: Activitățile modulului TN6

Figura 8: Fișierul cu resurse al modului TN1

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Certificarea finală

După finalizarea tuturor secțiunilor din cursul **TN (Train-the-Trainer)** sau **WN (Mentenanță Predictivă)**, utilizatorii vor **debloca o nouă secțiune** care conține **testul final cuprinzător**.

- **Testul final** include **25 de întrebări aleatorii**, selectate din toate secțiunile cursului.
- **Promovarea acestui test este obligatorie** pentru obținerea certificării finale a cursului.

Certificat de finalizare

După promovarea testului final, cursanții vor primi un **certificat oficial**, care va conține:

- ✓ Numele complet al utilizatorului
- ✓ Numele cursului
- ✓ Titlul secțiunii (dacă este aplicabil)
- ✓ Data emiterii certificatului
- ✓ Cod de verificare unic
- ✓ Cod QR pentru verificare rapidă

Codul QR permite validarea certificatului direct de pe dispozitive mobile, iar toate certificatele pot fi **verificate prin platforma PreMETS** pentru a confirma autenticitatea acestora (figura 9).

Figura 9: Exemplu diploma de certificare

Cursurile de pe platforma PreMETS includ un **tablou de anunțuri** (figura 10) și un **forum de discuții** (figura 11).

Tabloul de anunțuri permite instructorilor sau administratorilor platformei să **partajeze actualizări importante**, notificări și noutăți legate de curs cu utilizatorii.

Forum-ul de discuții oferă un spațiu interactiv în care studenții pot **comunica cu alți cursanți și instructori**, pot pune întrebări, schimba idei și se pot angaja în **învățare colaborativă**.

The screenshot shows the PreMETS interface. At the top, there's a navigation bar with 'Home', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Site administration'. The main header includes the PreMETS logo and 'Edit mode' toggle. A left sidebar menu is open, showing 'General' with 'Announcements' selected, and 'TN1: Learner happiness, moti...' with various quiz and lecture options. The main content area is titled 'Announcements' and shows a search bar, an 'Add discussion topic' button, and a table of discussions. The table has columns for 'Discussion', 'Started by', 'Last post', and 'Replies'. Two discussions are listed: 'PreMETS Certification' and 'Train-the-Trainers Pre-Pilot 14-18/10/2024', both started by 'Afroditi Anagno...' on October 17 and 15, 2024, respectively, with 0 replies. At the bottom, there are logos for the European Union, CERTH, and CERTH/HIT, along with funding information.

Figura 10: Anunțurile cursurilor TN

The screenshot shows the PreMETS forum interface. The navigation bar and sidebar are similar to the previous screenshot. The main content area is titled 'Forum' and shows a discussion titled 'Questions for TN1 - TN4'. The discussion is by 'Afroditi Anagnostopoulou' on Tuesday, 15 October 2024, at 3:09 PM. The content of the post says: 'Should you have any questions or require further information, please let us know!'. There are buttons for 'Permalink', 'Edit', 'Delete', and 'Reply'. At the bottom, there are logos for the European Union, CERTH, and CERTH/HIT, along with funding information.

Figura 11: Forumul cursului TN

4. Platform

Platforma PreMETS oferă o gamă de caracteristici concepute pentru a sprijini atât învățarea, cât și interacțiunea utilizatorilor:

Fiecare utilizator înregistrat dispune de o **pagină de profil personalizată** (figura 12), unde poate:

- Vizualiza și edita informațiile personale (cum ar fi numele, adresa de e-mail etc.).
- Descărca certificatele pentru cursurile finalizate.
- Solicita toate datele colectate de platformă referitoare la activitatea lor.
- **Șterge datele personale:** Utilizatorii pot alege să își **șteargă contul și toate datele asociate**, însă acest lucru va elimina și posibilitatea de a valida orice certificare obținută.

The screenshot displays the 'PreMETS Administrator' profile page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'PreMETS', 'Home', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Site administration'. A 'Reset page to default' button is visible. The profile is for a user named 'PA'. The main content area is divided into several sections:

- User details:** Includes fields for Email address (support@premets-platform.eu), Country of residence (Greece), City/town (Piraeus), Timezone (Europe/Athens), Country (GR), Nationality (Greek), Gender (Male), Age range (25-34), Learning difficulties (None), Educational level (Doctorate or higher), Employment status (Employed full-time), and Employment sector (Information Technology). An 'Edit profile' link is present.
- Miscellaneous:** Contains links for Notes, My certificates, Forum posts, Forum discussions, and Learning plans.
- Reports:** Includes links for Today's logs, All logs, Outline report, Complete report, Browser sessions, Grades overview, and Grades.
- Login activity:** Shows 'First access to site' on Friday, 19 July 2024, and 'Last access to site' on Monday, 17 March 2025. It also lists the 'Last IP address' as 172.71.144.35.
- Mobile app:** Features a 'QR code for mobile app access' and a note about security. It also shows the 'Last access to site' on Friday, 8 November 2024.
- Privacy and policies:** Provides links for 'Contact the privacy officer', 'Data requests', 'Export all of my personal data', and 'Policies and agreements'.
- Course details:** Lists 'Course profiles' such as 'TN: Train-the-Trainer' and 'WN: Predictive Maintenance'.

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Figura 12: Opțiunile unui utilizator PREMETS

Tabloul Global de Anunțuri

Platforma include un **tablou global de anunțuri**, unde utilizatorii pot vizualiza actualizări și notificări importante postate de administratorii platformei sau instructorii cursurilor. Această funcționalitate ajută utilizatorii să fie la curent cu **noi conținuturi, evenimente viitoare sau noutăți legate de platformă**.

Calendarul Evenimentelor

Calendarul afișează toate evenimentele relevante, cum ar fi **termenele limită ale cursurilor**, **webinarii** și **programul de întreținere al sistemului** (figura 13). Utilizatorii pot accesa acest calendar pentru a se asigura că nu ratează datele importante.

Figura 13: Exemplu de eveniment in calendar "WN - Pre-Pilot Timisoara Ziua 3"

Accesibilitate și Suport Multilingv

PreMETS este conceput pentru a fi prietenos cu utilizatorii cu nevoi de accesibilitate, având instrumente și funcționalități verificate prin audituri externe de accesibilitate. Platforma susține o gamă largă de nevoi de accesibilitate, inclusiv **cititoare de ecran** și **opțiuni de navigare alternative**.

De asemenea, utilizatorii pot selecta limba preferată prin meniul de limbi al platformei. Deși limba **engleză** este complet suportată, o **proporție semnificativă** din conținutul platformei este tradusă în alte limbi. Acest lucru ajută la asigurarea accesibilității platformei pentru utilizatorii din diverse medii lingvistice.

Politicile Platformei

Platforma este guvernată de trei politici principale: **Termenii de utilizare**, **Politica privind cookie-urile** și **Politica de confidențialitate**.

- **Termenii de utilizare** explică regulile și ghidurile pe care utilizatorii trebuie să le urmeze atunci când accesează sau utilizează platforma. Aceștia acoperă responsabilitățile atât ale platformei, cât și ale utilizatorului, incluzând comportamentul acceptabil, restricțiile de utilizare și consecințele încălcării acestor termeni. De asemenea, sunt tratate considerațiile legale, precum drepturile de proprietate intelectuală, declinările de responsabilitate și limitările de răspundere, servind practic ca un acord între utilizator și platformă privind modul în care poate fi utilizat serviciul.
- **Politica privind cookie-urile** explică modul în care platforma utilizează cookie-uri pentru a îmbunătăți experiența utilizatorului. Cookie-urile sunt fișiere mici de text stocate pe dispozitivul utilizatorului care ajută platforma să rețină anumite detalii, cum ar fi preferințele, informațiile de autentificare sau să urmărească modul în care este utilizat site-ul. Această politică detaliază tipurile de cookie-uri utilizate, motivele pentru utilizarea acestora (de exemplu, pentru funcționalitate sau marketing) și furnizează instrucțiuni pentru utilizatori despre cum să gestioneze sau să dezactiveze cookie-urile în setările browserului lor.
- **Politica de confidențialitate** descrie modul în care platforma colectează, stochează și protejează datele personale ale utilizatorilor. Explică tipurile de informații personale colectate, cum ar fi numele, adresele de e-mail sau detaliile de plată, și modul în care aceste informații sunt utilizate, fie pentru îmbunătățirea serviciilor, fie pentru comunicare. Politica de confidențialitate abordează, de asemenea, modul în care platforma poate împărtăși datele cu terțe părți și informează utilizatorii despre drepturile lor de a accesa, actualiza sau șterge informațiile lor personale.

Toate politicile pot fi consultate la următorul link: <https://premets-platform.eu/admin/tool/policy/viewall.php>

5. Concluzii

Platforma PreMETS este un **mediu complet și ușor de utilizat**, care oferă training de înaltă calitate în **Mentenanța Predictivă**. Cu o **interfață intuitivă**, resurse de învățare diverse și o gamă variată de funcționalități interactive, PreMETS permite cursanților să dezvolte **abilități esențiale** într-un mediu colaborativ și captivant.

Urmând acest manual, utilizatorii pot naviga cu ușurință pe platformă, pot accesa cursuri, pot finaliza chestionare și pot primi certificări valoroase după finalizarea cursurilor. Indiferent că sunt cursanți, instructori sau administratori ai platformei, PreMETS oferă toate instrumentele necesare pentru o **experiență educațională de succes**.

Serbian Version

1. Uvod

PreMETS platforma je inovativno obrazovno okruženje izgrađeno na Moodle-u, sistemu upravljanja učenjem otvorenog koda (LMS). Nudi specijalizovanu obuku u dve ključne oblasti: TN: Obučiti-trenera i VN: Prediktivno održavanje. Platforma je dizajnirana da podrži tehničku ekspertizu i razvoj nastave, pružajući učenicima interaktivni i zanimljiv obrazovni sadržaj. Kroz različite aktivnosti—uključujući kvizove, video zapise sa uputstvima i forume za diskusiju—korisnici mogu pristupiti vrednim resursima prilagođenim njihovim individualnim potrebama učenja.

PreMETS je globalno dostupan preko mreže za isporuku sadržaja (CDN), osiguravajući brz i pouzdan pristup u različitim regionima, a hostuje se na Microsoft Aure računarstvu u oblaku. Platforma je višejezična, podržava sledeće jezike: engleski, nemački, italijanski, holandski, rumunski, srpski i grčki. Platforma je dostupna na <https://premets-platform.eu> (slika 1).

Da bi poboljšao iskustvo učenja, PreMETS uključuje prilagodljive metodologije učenja, omogućavajući korisnicima da napreduju sopstvenim tempom na osnovu njihovog nivoa znanja i učinka. Koristeći analitiku podataka i povratne informacije korisnika, platforma kontinuirano usavršava svoj sadržaj i metode isporuke kako bi optimizovala angažovanje i zadržavanje znanja. Ovaj personalizovani pristup osigurava da i treneri i tehnički profesionalci dobiju ciljana i efikasna uputstva prilagođena njihovim specifičnim potrebama.

PreMETS: Predictive Maintenance Education and Training System

Welcome to the **PreMETS: Predictive Maintenance Education and Training System**. PreMETS is an alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education and training. In PreMETS, collaboration and knowledge sharing are crucial to promote connectivity, inclusivity, innovation, and equal access to high-quality education in Predictive Maintenance.

Predictive Maintenance (PM) is crucial for optimizing economic resources and fundamental infrastructure systems. Its primary function is to foresee and prevent critical infrastructure breakdowns or failures through digital approaches.

This digital education platform contains two educational programs:

1. the **WN: Predictive Maintenance** which integrates both higher education and vocational education standards and
2. the **TN: Train-the-Trainer** for academic, vocational, and corporate levels, enhancing accessibility and effectiveness of PM education.

These courses offer a micro-credential certificate, offering recognition and certification for PM skills for both learners and trainers.

Available courses

TN: Train-the-Trainer

Teacher: PreMETS Administrator

WN: Predictive Maintenance

Teacher: PreMETS Administrator

Site announcements

There are no discussion topics yet in this forum

Upcoming events

There are no upcoming events
[Go to calendar...](#)

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Slika 1: Početna strana platforme

2. Registracija

Za pristup kursevima i sadržajima na PreMETS platformi potrebna je registracija korisnika (slika 2). Registracija je jednostavna i može se izvršiti putem e-pošte ili registracijom pomoću Google ili Microsoft naloga (slika 3).

Slika 2: Stranica za prijavu na platformu

Koraci za registraciju:

1. Prihvatite smernice platforme: Tokom registracije, potrebno je pregledati i prihvatiti dokumente o uslovima korišćenja, politici kolačića i politici privatnosti platforme.
2. Popunite obavezna polja: Obrazac za registraciju će tražiti osnovne informacije kao što su ime i prezime, država, korisničko ime, adresa e-pošte i lozinka.

Takođe će biti data opcija da popunite demografsku anketu koja uključuje polja:

- Nacionalnost
- Pol
- Starosni raspon
- Poteškoće u učenju
- Obrazovni nivo
- Status zaposlenja
- Sektor zapošljavanja

Kada se registracija završi i e-mail adresa bude verifikovana, korisnici će imati pristup svim funkcijama i sadržaju platforme. Ovo uključuje upis na kurseve, učešće u diskusijama i učešće u procenama.

New account

Username ⓘ

The password must have at least 8 characters, at least 1 digit(s), at least 1 lower case letter(s), at least 1 upper case letter(s), at least 1 special character(s) such as *, -, or #

Password ⓘ

Email address ⓘ

Email (again) ⓘ

First name ⓘ

Last name ⓘ

City/Town

Country of residence ⓘ

Select a country ⌵

Demographic Information

The demographic fields provided below are intended exclusively for analytics and research purposes. We assure you that all information submitted will be treated with the utmost confidentiality and will be accessible solely to you. Neither your instructors nor any other users will have access to this data.

By completing these fields, you will significantly contribute to the enhancement of our services. We kindly request that you take a moment to provide this information. Your participation is highly valuable to us. You can update your selections in your profile at any time.

Thank you for your support.

Nationality ⓘ

Prefer not to say ⌵

Gender ⓘ

Prefer not to say ⌵

Age range ⓘ

Prefer not to say ⌵

Learning difficulties ⓘ

Prefer not to say ⌵

Educational level ⓘ

Prefer not to say ⌵

Employment status ⓘ

Prefer not to say ⌵

Employment sector ⓘ

Prefer not to say ⌵

Security question ⓘ

I'm not a robot

[Create my new account](#) [Cancel](#)

ⓘ Required

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Slika 3: Registraciona forma platforme

3. Kursevi

PreMETS platforma nudi dva osnovna kursa (slika 4): Obučiti-trenera (TN) i Prediktivno održavanje (VN). Svaki kurs je podjeljen na nekoliko sekcija koje se fokusiraju na različite aspekte predmeta.

Available courses

TN: Train-the-Trainer 🔑

Teacher: [PreMETS Administrator](#)

WN: Predictive Maintenance ➡️

Teacher: [PreMETS Administrator](#)

Slika 4: Dostupni kursevi platforme

TN: Obučiti-trenera

Ovaj kurs je osmišljen da pomogne nastavnicima da razviju efikasne strategije za pružanje obuke i podsticanje angažovanja učenika. Podjeljen je na 8 delova, od kojih svaki pokriva različite elemente nastave i učenja (slika 5).

- TN1: Strategije sreće, motivacije, angažovanja i učinka učenika
- TN2: Smanjenje procenta napuštanja onlajn obrazovanja
- TN3: Inkluzivne i personalizovane strategije obrazovanja za onlajn isporuku u visokom i stručnom obrazovanju
- TN4: Plastičnost mozga i veze učenja
- TN5: Kvalitativni i efikasni otvoreni obrazovni resursi
- TN6: Smernice za etičku analizu učenika za oblast preventivnog održavanja
- TN7: Mikroakreditacioni sistemi i sertifikacija veština
- TN8: (Ponovno) korišćenje postojeće infrastrukture i resursa za učenje

WN: Prediktivno održavanje

Ovaj kurs se fokusira na tehničke i strateške elemente prediktivnog održavanja, dizajniran za profesionalce koji rade u tehničkim oblastima (slika 6). Sastoji se od 6 sekcija:

- WN1: Holističke kompetencije prediktivnog održavanja
- WN2: kompetencije digitalnih veština za prediktivno održavanje
- WN3: kompetencije zelenih veština za prediktivno održavanje
- WN4: Kompetencije otpornosti za prediktivno održavanje
- WN5: Inovacione i preduzetničke kompetencije
- WN6: Ponovno učenje kako učiti u digitalnom okruženju

The screenshot shows the PreMETS user interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'PreMETS', 'Home', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Site administration'. On the right, there are user profile icons and an 'Edit mode' toggle. A left-hand sidebar menu is open, showing a tree structure of course sections. The main content area is titled 'TN: Train-the-Trainer' and includes sub-tabs for 'Course', 'Settings', 'Participants', 'Grades', 'Reports', and 'More'. The 'General' section is active, displaying a list of course sections with their respective activity counts and progress indicators. A 'Course Completion' section is also visible at the bottom of the list.

Section Name	Activities	Progress
General		
Announcements		
Forum		
License		
TN1: Learner happiness, moti...		
TN1: Video Lecture		
TN1: Material		
TN1: Practise Quiz		
TN1: Final Quiz		
TN1: "Learner happiness, m...		
TN2: Reducing the percentag...		
TN2: Video Lecture		
TN2: Material		
TN2: Practise Quiz		
TN2: Final Quiz		
TN3: Inclusive and Personalized Education in Predictive Maintenance Strategies for Online Deliveries in Higher and Vocational Education and Beyond	5	0 / 4
TN4: Brain Plasticity and Learning Connections	5	0 / 4
TN5: Qualitative & effective open educational resources	6	0 / 5
TN6: Ethical learner analytics guidelines for preventive maintenance field	6	0 / 5
TN7: Microcredential systems and skill certification	6	0 / 5
TN8: (Re)use existing infrastructures and learning resources	6	0 / 5
Course Completion	2	0 / 1

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Slika 5: TN kurs i njegove sekcije

The screenshot shows the PreMETS course interface for 'WN: Predictive Maintenance'. The top navigation bar includes 'Home', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Site administration'. The course title 'WN: Predictive Maintenance' is displayed at the top of the main content area. Below the title, there are tabs for 'Course', 'Settings', 'Participants', 'Grades', 'Reports', and 'More'. The main content area is divided into several sections, each with a title and a progress indicator:

- General**: Includes 'Announcements' and 'Forum'. A note states: 'PreMETS materials are licensed under Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0 International'.
- WN1: Holistic PM competences**: Progress: 0 / 4
- WN2: Digital skills competences for PM**: Progress: 0 / 4
- WN3: Green skills competences for PM**: Progress: 0 / 4
- WN4: Resilience competences for PM**: Progress: 0 / 4
- WN5: Innovation & entrepreneurship competences**: Progress: 0 / 4
- WN6: Relearning how to learn in a digital environment**: Progress: 0 / 4
- Completion**: Progress: 0 / 1

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Slika 6: WN kurs i njegove sekcije

Svaki deo kursa uključuje (slika 7):

- Video predavanja: Svaki odeljak sadrži video koji objašnjava ključne koncepte. U nekim slučajevima, video snimci predstavljaju instruktora koji predstavlja materijal.
- Materijali za kurs (slika 8): Svaki odeljak dolazi sa materijalima koji se mogu preuzeti, kao što su brošure, slajdovi, ploče priča i veb upiti, koji su dostupni na svim podržanim jezicima.
- Kvizovi: Svaki odeljak sadrži dve vrste kvizova:
 - Kviz za vežbanje: Uključuje 5 nasumičnih pitanja, gde učenici dobijaju povratne informacije odmah nakon podnošenja. Za kviz za vežbanje se ne beleži rezultat.
 - Finalni kviz: Sadrži 10 nasumičnih pitanja iz sadržaja sekcije. Povratne informacije nisu obezbeđene, a učenici moraju postići prolaznu ocenu da bi napredovali. Ovaj kviz je neophodan za završetak kursa.
- Sertifikacija: Nakon procesa učenja i položenog završnog kviza, korisnicima se dodeljuje sertifikat o završenom odeljku.

PreMETS Home Dashboard My courses Site administration PA Edit mode

TN / TN6: Ethical learner analytics guidelines for preventive maintenance field

TN6: Ethical learner analytics guidelines for preventive maintenance field

Video Lecture with Instructor Mark as done

Video Lecture Mark as done

- TN6: Material Mark as done
- TN6: Practise Quiz To do
- Not available unless: The activity TN6: Video Lecture with Instructor is marked complet... [Show more](#)
- TN6: Final Quiz To do
- Not available unless: The activity TN6: Practise Quiz is marked complete
- TN6: "Ethical learner analytics guidelines for preventive maintenance field" Certificate To do
- Not available unless: The activity TN6: Final Quiz is marked complete

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Slika 7: TN6 aktivnosti u sekcijama

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Slika 8: TN1 folder sa materijalima

Svi materijali platforme PreMETS su licencirani pod međunarodnom licencom Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0, omogućavajući korisnicima da slobodno pristupaju i dele sadržaj uz odgovarajuće pripisivanje, ali ne u komercijalne svrhe i bez mogućnosti modifikacije materijala.

Po završetku svih sekcija u TN ili VN kursu, korisnici će otključati novi odeljak koji sadrži završni sveobuhvatni kviz. Ovaj završni kviz uključuje 25 nasumičnih pitanja odabranih iz svih sekcija kursa. Uspešno završen završni kviz je neophodan da bi učenik dobio sertifikat za završni kurs.

Nakon što polože završni kviz, učenici će dobiti sertifikat koji uključuje njihovo puno ime, naziv kursa, naslov odeljka (ako je primenljivo), naziv kursa, datum izdavanja, verifikacioni kod i QR kod. QR kod omogućava lako verifikaciju sertifikata pomoću mobilnih uređaja. Svi sertifikati mogu biti validirani preko PreMETS platforme da bi se potvrdila njihova autentičnost (slika 9).

CERTIFICATE OF COMPLETION

is awarded to
PreMETS Administrator

for completing their course *WN: Predictive Maintenance*
WNI: Holistic PM competences

Issue Date: *September 17, 2024*
Verification code: *M1iZiLrhoU*
Verify at: <https://premets-platform.eu/ver-cert>

Slika 9: Primer sertifikata

Kursevi na PreMETS platformi uključuju oglasnu tablu (slika 10) i forum za diskusiju (slika 11). Oglasna tabla omogućava instruktorima ili administratorima platforme da dele važna ažuriranja, obaveštenja i vesti u vezi sa kursom sa korisnicima. Forum za diskusiju pruža interaktivni prostor gde studenti mogu da komuniciraju sa drugim učenicima i instruktorima, postavljaju pitanja, razmenjuju ideje i učestvuju u zajedničkom učenju.

PreMETS Home Dashboard My courses Site administration PA Edit mode

General Announcements Forum License

TN1: Learner happiness, moti...
TN1: Video Lecture
TN1: Material
TN1: Practise Quiz
TN1: Final Quiz
TN1: "Learner happiness, m...
TN2: Reducing the percentag...
TN2: Video Lecture
TN2: Material
TN2: Practise Quiz
TN2: Final Quiz

TN / General / Announcements

Announcements

Forum Settings Advanced grading Subscriptions Reports More

General news and announcements

Search forums Add discussion topic

Discussion	Started by	Last post ↓	Replies
☆ PreMETS Certification	Afroditi Anagno... 17 Oct 2024	Afroditi Anagno... 17 Oct 2024	0
☆ Train-the-Trainers Pre-Pilot 14-18/10/2024	Afroditi Anagno... 15 Oct 2024	Afroditi Anagno... 15 Oct 2024	0

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CERTH CENTRE FOR RESEARCH & TECHNOLOGY HELLAS

CERTH/HT Hellenic Institute of Transport

The PreMETS Project has received funding from ERASMUS2027 programme, ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PI-ALL-INNO call, under grant agreement No. 101108469

The PreMETS Platform was developed and is maintained by the CERTH/HT

Slika 10: Obaveštenja na TN kursu

The screenshot displays the PreMETS platform interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'Home', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Site administration'. A user profile 'PA' and an 'Edit mode' toggle are also visible. A left-hand sidebar contains a menu with categories like 'General', 'License', and various course topics such as 'TN1: Learner happiness, moti...' and 'TN2: Reducing the percentag...'. The main content area shows a forum thread titled 'Questions for TN1 - TN4'. The thread is posted by 'Afrediti Anagnostopoulou' on Tuesday, 15 October 2024, at 3:09 PM. The message content reads: 'Should you have any questions or require further information, please let us know!'. Below the message are options for 'Permalink', 'Edit', 'Delete', and 'Reply'. The forum interface includes controls for displaying replies in a nested form and moving the discussion. At the bottom of the page, there are logos for the European Union, CERTH (Centre for Research & Technology Hellas), and CERTH/HIT (Hellenic Institute of Transport). Text at the bottom states: 'The PreMETS Project has received funding from ERASMUS2027 programme, ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PI-ALL-INNO call, under grant agreement No. 101108469' and 'The PreMETS Platform was developed and is maintained by the CERTH/HIT'.

Slika 11: Forum TN kursa

4. Platforma

PreMETS platforma nudi niz funkcija dizajniranih da podrže učenje i interakciju korisnika:

Svaki registrovani korisnik ima personalizovanu stranicu profila (slika 12), na kojoj može:

- Pregledati i urediti lične podatke (kao što su ime, adresa e-pošte, itd.).
- Preuzeti sertifikate o završenim kursevima.
- Zahtevati sve podatke koje platforma prikuplja u vezi sa njegovom aktivnošću.
- Brisati lične podatke: Korisnici mogu da izaberu da izbrišu svoj nalog i sve povezane podatke, iako će to takođe ukloniti mogućnost verifikacije bilo kakvih sertifikata.

The screenshot displays the 'PreMETS Administrator' profile page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'PreMETS', 'Home', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Site administration'. A user profile icon is visible, along with 'PA' and 'Edit mode' options. A 'Reset page to default' button is located at the top right. The main content area is titled 'PA PreMETS Administrator' and is divided into several sections:

- User details:** Includes 'Email address' (support@premets-platform.eu), 'Country of residence' (Greece), 'City/town' (Piraeus), 'Timezone' (Europe/Athens), 'Country' (GR), 'Nationality' (Greek), 'Gender' (Male), 'Age range' (25-34), 'Learning difficulties' (None), 'Educational level' (Doctorate or higher), 'Employment status' (Employed full-time), and 'Employment sector' (Information Technology). There is an 'Edit profile' link.
- Miscellaneous:** Contains links for 'Notes', 'My certificates', 'Forum posts', 'Forum discussions', and 'Learning plans'.
- Reports:** Contains links for 'Today's logs', 'All logs', 'Outline report', 'Complete report', 'Browser sessions', 'Grades overview', and 'Grades'.
- Login activity:** Shows 'First access to site' (Friday, 19 July 2024, 3:27 PM) and 'Last access to site' (Monday, 17 March 2025, 1:22 PM). It also lists the 'Last IP address' as 172.71.144.35.
- Mobile app:** Includes a 'QR code for mobile app access' and a note that QR login is not allowed for site administrators. It also shows the 'Last access to site' (Friday, 8 November 2024, 8:03 AM).
- Privacy and policies:** Contains links for 'Contact the privacy officer', 'Data requests', 'Export all of my personal data', and 'Policies and agreements'.
- Course details:** Lists 'Course profiles' for 'TN: Train-the-Trainer' and 'WN: Predictive Maintenance'.

The PreMETS Project has received funding from ERASMUS2027 programme, ERASMUS-EDU-2022-PI-ALL-INNO call, under grant agreement No. 101108469

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The PreMETS Platform was developed and is maintained by the CERTH/HIT

Slika 12: Primer stranice profila sa korisničkim opcijama i informacijama

Globalna oglasna tabla

Platforma uključuje globalnu tablu za najave na kojoj korisnici mogu da vide ažuriranja i važna obaveštenja koja postavljaju administratori platforme ili instruktori kurseva. Ova funkcija pomaže korisnicima da budu informisani o novom sadržaju, predstojećim događajima ili vestima u vezi sa platformom.

Kalendar događaja

Kalendar prikazuje sve relevantne događaje, kao što su predstojeći rokovi kurseva, vebinari i rasporedi održavanja sistema (slika 13). Korisnici mogu pristupiti ovom kalendaru da bi bili u toku sa važnim datumima.

Slika 13: Primer kalendarskog događaja, „WN - Pre-Pilot Temišvar dan 3“

Pristupačnost i višejezična podrška

PreMETS je dizajniran da bude prilagođen pristupačnosti, sa alatima i funkcijama verifikovanim spoljnim revizijama pristupačnosti. Platforma podržava širok spektar potreba za pristupačnošću, uključujući čitače ekrana i alternativne opcije navigacije.

Pored toga, korisnici mogu da izaberu svoj željeni jezik preko jezičkog menija platforme. Iako je engleski u potpunosti podržan, značajan deo sadržaja platforme je preveden na druge jezike. Ovo pomaže da se osigura da je platforma dostupna korisnicima iz različitih lingvističkih sredina.

Platformu upravljaju tri glavne politike: Uslovi korišćenja, Politika kolačića i Politika privatnosti.

- Uslovi korišćenja navode pravila i smernice koje korisnici moraju da poštuju kada pristupaju ili koriste platformu. Pokriva odgovornosti i platforme i korisnika, uključujući prihvatljivo ponašanje, ograničenja korišćenja i posledice za kršenje ovih uslova. Takođe se bavi pravnim razmatranjima kao što su prava intelektualne svojine, odricanje odgovornosti i ograničenja odgovornosti, u suštini služeći kao sporazum između korisnika i platforme o tome kako se usluga može koristiti.
- Politika kolačića objašnjava kako platforma koristi kolačiće za poboljšanje korisničkog iskustva. Kolačići su male tekstualne datoteke koje se čuvaju na uređaju korisnika i pomažu platformi da zapamti određene detalje kao što su preferencije, informacije za prijavu ili praćenje načina na koji se sajt koristi. Ova politika detaljno opisuje tipove kolačića koji se koriste, razloge za njihovo korišćenje (kao što su funkcionalnost ili marketing) i pruža uputstva korisnicima o tome kako da upravljaju ili onemoguće kolačiće u podešavanjima pregledača.
- Politika privatnosti opisuje kako platforma prikuplja, čuva i štiti lične podatke korisnika. Objašnjava vrste ličnih informacija koje se prikupljaju, kao što su imena, adrese e-pošte ili detalji plaćanja, i kako se te informacije koriste, bilo za poboljšanje usluga ili komunikacije. Politika se takođe bavi načinom na koji platforma može da deli podatke sa trećim licima i obaveštava korisnike o njihovim pravima na pristup, ažuriranje ili brisanje njihovih ličnih podataka.

Sve polise se nalaze na sledećem linku: <https://premets-platform.eu/admin/tool/policy/viewall.php>

5. Zaključak

PreMETS platforma je sveobuhvatno okruženje prilagođeno korisniku koje nudi visokokvalitetnu obuku iz prediktivnog održavanja. Sa intuitivnim interfejsom, raznovrsnim resursima za učenje i nizom interaktivnih funkcija, PreMETS omogućava učenicima da razviju kritične veštine u okruženju za saradnju i angažovanje.

Prateći ovaj priručnik, korisnici mogu lako da se kreću platformom, pristupaju kursevima, ispunjavaju kvizove i dobijaju vredne sertifikate po završetku kursa. Bilo da ste učenik, instruktor ili administrator platforme, PreMETS pruža sve alate neophodne za uspešno obrazovno iskustvo.

Greek Version

1. Εισαγωγή

Η πλατφόρμα PreMETS είναι ένα καινοτόμο εκπαιδευτικό περιβάλλον που βασίζεται στο Moodle, ένα Σύστημα Διαχείρισης Μάθησης ανοιχτού κώδικα (ΣΔΜ). Προσφέρει εξειδικευμένη εκπαίδευση σε δύο βασικούς τομείς: TN: Train-the-Trainer και WN: Predictive Maintenance. Η πλατφόρμα έχει σχεδιαστεί για να υποστηρίζει τόσο την τεχνική εμπειρογνωμοσύνη όσο και την εκπαιδευτική ανάπτυξη, παρέχοντας στους μαθητές διαδραστικό και ελκυστικό εκπαιδευτικό περιεχόμενο. Μέσα από μια ποικιλία δραστηριοτήτων, συμπεριλαμβανομένων κουίζ, εκπαιδευτικών βίντεο και φόρουμ, οι χρήστες μπορούν να έχουν πρόσβαση σε πολύτιμους πόρους προσαρμοσμένους στις ατομικές τους μαθησιακές ανάγκες.

Το PreMETS είναι παγκοσμίως προσβάσιμο μέσω ενός Δικτύου Παράδοσης Περιεχομένου (CDN), διασφαλίζοντας γρήγορη και αξιόπιστη πρόσβαση σε διαφορετικές περιοχές και φιλοξενείται στο Microsoft Azure cloud computing. Η πλατφόρμα είναι πολύγλωσση και υποστηρίζει τις ακόλουθες γλώσσες: Αγγλικά, Γερμανικά, Ιταλικά, Ολλανδικά, Ρουμανικά, Σερβικά και Ελληνικά. Η πλατφόρμα είναι προσβάσιμη στη διεύθυνση <https://premets-platform.eu> (Εικόνα 1).

Για τη βελτίωση της μαθησιακής εμπειρίας, το PreMETS ενσωματώνει προσαρμοστικές μεθοδολογίες μάθησης, επιτρέποντας στους χρήστες να προοδεύουν με τον δικό τους ρυθμό με βάση το επίπεδο γνώσης και τις επιδόσεις τους. Αξιοποιώντας την ανάλυση δεδομένων και τα σχόλια των χρηστών, η πλατφόρμα βελτιώνει συνεχώς το περιεχόμενο και τις μεθόδους παράδοσης για να βελτιστοποιήσει την αφοσίωση και τη διατήρηση της γνώσης. Αυτή η εξατομικευμένη προσέγγιση διασφαλίζει ότι τόσο οι εκπαιδευτές όσο και οι τεχνικοί επαγγελματίες λαμβάνουν στοχευμένες και αποτελεσματικές οδηγίες προσαρμοσμένες στις ανάγκες τους.

PreMETS: Σύστημα Εκπαίδευσης και Κατάρτισης για την Προβλεπτική Συντήρηση

Καλώς ήρθατε στην πλατφόρμα **PreMETS: Σύστημα Εκπαίδευσης και Κατάρτισης για την Προβλεπτική Συντήρηση**. Μια συμμαχία για την ενίσχυση της ευρωπαϊκής καινοτομίας στην Προβλεπτική Συντήρηση μέσω της επιχειρηματικής συνεργασίας, της εκπαίδευσης και της κατάρτισης. Στο PreMETS, η συνεργασία και η ανταλλαγή γνώσεων είναι ζωτικής σημασίας για την προώθηση της συνδεσιμότητας, της συμπεριλήψης, της καινοτομίας και της ίσης πρόσβασης σε εκπαίδευση υψηλής ποιότητας στην Προγνωστική Συντήρηση.

Η **Προγνωστική Συντήρηση (ΠΣ)** είναι ζωτικής σημασίας για τη βελτιστοποίηση των οικονομικών πόρων και των θεμελιωδών συστημάτων υποδομής. Η κύρια λειτουργία του είναι να προβλέπει και να αποτρέπει βλάβες ή αστοχίες κρίσιμων υποδομών μέσω ψηφιακών προσεγγίσεων. Η πλατφόρμα ψηφιακής εκπαίδευσης περιλαμβάνει δύο εκπαιδευτικά προγράμματα:

1. το **WN: Προγνωστική Συντήρηση** που ενσωματώνει τόσο τα πρότυπα τριτοβάθμιας εκπαίδευσης όσο και τα πρότυπα επαγγελματικής εκπαίδευσης και
2. το **TN: Train-the-Trainer** σε ακαδημαϊκό, επαγγελματικό και εταιρικό επίπεδο, ενισχύοντας την προσαρμοστικότητα και την αποτελεσματικότητα της εκπαίδευσης για την Προγνωστική Συντήρηση.

Τα προγράμματα αυτά προσφέρουν ένα πιστοποιητικό μικρο-διαπιστευτηρίων, προσφέροντας αναγνώριση και πιστοποίηση για τις δεξιότητες της ΠΣ τόσο για μαθητές όσο και για εκπαιδευτές.

Διαθέσιμα μαθήματα

TN: Train-the-Trainer

Διδάσκων: PreMETS Administrator

WN: Προγνωστική Συντήρηση

Διδάσκων: PreMETS Administrator

Ανακοινώσεις Ιστοσελίδας

Δεν υπάρχουν ακόμα θέματα συζήτησης σε αυτό το φόρουμ

Επικείμενα γεγονότα

Κανένα επικείμενο γεγονός
Μετάβαση στο ημερολόγιο...

Εικόνα 1: Ιστοσελίδα της Πλατφόρμας

2. Εγγραφή

Για πρόσβαση στα μαθήματα και το περιεχόμενο της πλατφόρμας PreMETS, απαιτείται εγγραφή χρήστη (Εικόνα 2). Η εγγραφή είναι απλή και μπορεί να ολοκληρωθεί μέσω email ή με εγγραφή σε λογαριασμό Google ή Microsoft (Εικόνα 3).

Εικόνα 2: Ιστοσελίδα για Σύνδεση και Εγγραφή στην πλατφόρμα

Βήματα για την εγγραφή:

1. Αποδεχτείτε τις πολιτικές της πλατφόρμας: Κατά την εγγραφή, απαιτείται έλεγχος και αποδοχή των Όρων Χρήσης, της Πολιτικής Cookies και της Πολιτικής Απορρήτου της πλατφόρμας.
2. Συμπληρώστε υποχρεωτικά πεδία: Η φόρμα εγγραφής θα ζητήσει βασικές πληροφορίες όπως όνομα και επώνυμο, χώρα, όνομα χρήστη, διεύθυνση email και κωδικό πρόσβασης.

Επίσης, θα σας δοθεί η επιλογή να συμπληρώσετε μια δημογραφική έρευνα που περιλαμβάνει πεδία:

- Εθνικότητα
- Φύλο
- Ηλικιακό εύρος
- Μαθησιακές δυσκολίες
- Μορφωτικό επίπεδο
- Εργασιακό καθεστώς
- Τομέας απασχόλησης

Μόλις ολοκληρωθεί η εγγραφή και επαληθευτεί η διεύθυνση email, οι χρήστες θα έχουν πρόσβαση σε όλες τις δυνατότητες και το περιεχόμενο της πλατφόρμας. Αυτό περιλαμβάνει την εγγραφή στα μαθήματα, τη συμμετοχή σε συζητήσεις και τη συμμετοχή σε αξιολογήσεις.

Νέος λογαριασμός

Όνομα χρήστη ¹

Ο κωδικός πρόσβασης πρέπει να έχει τουλάχιστον 8 χαρακτήρες, τουλάχιστον 1 ψηφίο/-α, τουλάχιστον 1 πεζό/-ά γράμμα/-τα, τουλάχιστον 1 κεφαλαίο/-α γράμμα/-τα, τουλάχιστον 1 μη αλφαριθμητικό/-ούς χαρακτήρα/-ες όπως *, - ή #

Κωδικός πρόσβασης ¹

Διεύθυνση ηλ.ταχυδρομείου ¹

Διεύθυνση ηλ.ταχυδρομείου (ξανά) ¹

Μικρό/Βαπτιστικό όνομα ¹

Επίθετο ¹

Πόλη/χωριό

Χώρα διαμονής ¹

Demographic Information

The demographic fields provided below are intended exclusively for analytics and research purposes. We assure you that all information submitted will be treated with the utmost confidentiality and will be accessible solely to you. Neither your instructors nor any other users will have access to this data.

By completing these fields, you will significantly contribute to the enhancement of our services. We kindly request that you take a moment to provide this information. Your participation is highly valuable to us. You can update your selections in your profile at any time.

Thank you for your support.

Nationality ¹

Prefer not to say

Gender ¹

Prefer not to say

Age range ¹

Prefer not to say

Learning difficulties ¹

Prefer not to say

Educational level ¹

Prefer not to say

Employment status ¹

Prefer not to say

Employment sector ¹

Prefer not to say

Ερώτηση ασφαλείας ²

Δεν είμαι ρομπότ

[Δημιουργία του λογαριασμού μου](#) [Άκυρο](#)

Υπάρχουν απαιτούμενα πεδία σε αυτή τη φόρμα που επισημαίνονται με ¹.

Εικόνα 3: Η φόρμα Εγγραφής στην πλατφόρμα

3. Μαθήματα

Η πλατφόρμα PreMETS προσφέρει δύο κύρια μαθήματα (Εικόνα 4): Train-the-Trainer - TN και Predictive Maintenance - WN. Κάθε μάθημα χωρίζεται σε πολλές ενότητες που εστιάζουν σε διαφορετικές πτυχές του αντικειμένου.

Διαθέσιμα μαθήματα

TN: Train-the-Trainer

Διδάσκων: PreMETS Administrator

WN: Προγνωστική Συντήρηση

Διδάσκων: PreMETS Administrator

Ανακοινώσεις Ιστοσελίδας

Απεγγραφή από αυτό το φόρουμ

Εικόνα 4: Διαθέσιμα μαθήματα στην Πλατφόρμα

TN: Train-the-Trainer

Αυτό το μάθημα έχει σχεδιαστεί για να βοηθήσει τους εκπαιδευτικούς να αναπτύξουν αποτελεσματικές στρατηγικές για την παροχή κατάρτισης και την προώθηση της εμπλοκής των μαθητών. Χωρίζεται σε 8 ενότητες, καθεμία από τις οποίες καλύπτει ένα διαφορετικό στοιχείο διδασκαλίας και μάθησης (Εικόνα 5).

- TN1: Ευτυχία, κίνητρα, δέσμευση και στρατηγικές απόδοσης των μαθητών
- TN2: Μείωση του ποσοστού εγκατάλειψης της διαδικτυακής εκπαίδευσης
- TN3: Χωρίς αποκλεισμούς και εξατομικευμένη εκπαίδευση σε στρατηγικές προληπτικής συντήρησης για διαδικτυακές παραδόσεις στην τριτοβάθμια και επαγγελματική εκπαίδευση και πέρα από αυτήν
- TN4: Πλαστικότητα εγκεφάλου και μαθησιακές συνδέσεις
- TN5: Ποιοτικοί και αποτελεσματικοί ανοιχτοί εκπαιδευτικοί πόροι
- TN6: Κατευθυντήριες γραμμές ανάλυσης ηθικών μαθητών για τον τομέα προληπτικής συντήρησης
- TN7: Συστήματα μικρο-διαπιστευτηρίων και πιστοποίηση δεξιοτήτων
- TN8: (Επανα)χρήση υφιστάμενων υποδομών και μαθησιακών πόρων

WN: Predictive Maintenance

Αυτό το μάθημα επικεντρώνεται στα τεχνικά και στρατηγικά στοιχεία της προγνωστικής συντήρησης, σχεδιασμένα για επαγγελματίες που εργάζονται σε τεχνικούς τομείς (Εικόνα 6). Αποτελείται από 6 ενότητες:

- WN1: Ολιστικές ικανότητες PM
- WN2: Ψηφιακές δεξιότητες για PM
- WN3: Πράσινες δεξιότητες για PM
- WN4: Ικανότητες ανθεκτικότητας για PM
- WN5: Ικανότητες Καινοτομίας & Επιχειρηματικότητας για PM
- WN6: Επανεκμάθηση πώς να μαθαίνετε σε ψηφιακό περιβάλλον

TN: Train-the-Trainer

[Μάθημα](#) [Συμμετέχοντες](#) [Βαθμοί](#) [Αναφορές](#) [Διακριτικά](#) [Περισσότερα](#) ▾

Γενικά →

Announcements

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TN1: Learner happiness, motivation, engagement and performance strategies →

Activities: 5 Πρόοδος: 0 / 4

TN2: Reducing the percentage of drop-outs from online education →

Activities: 5 Πρόοδος: 0 / 4

TN3: Inclusive and Personalized Education in Predictive Maintenance Strategies for Online Deliveries in Higher and Vocational Education and Beyond →

Activities: 5 Πρόοδος: 0 / 4

TN4: Brain Plasticity and Learning Connections →

Activities: 5 Πρόοδος: 0 / 4

TN5: Qualitative & effective open educational resources →

Activities: 6 Πρόοδος: 0 / 5

TN6: Ethical learner analytics guidelines for preventive maintenance field →

Activities: 6 Πρόοδος: 0 / 5

TN7: Microcredential systems and skill certification →

Activities: 6 Πρόοδος: 0 / 5

TN8: (Re)use existing infrastructures and learning resources →

Activities: 6 Πρόοδος: 0 / 5

Course Completion →

Activities: 2 Πρόοδος: 0 / 1

Εικόνα 5: Μάθημα TN και οι ενότητες του

WN: Προγνωστική Συντήρηση

Μάθημα Συμμετέχοντες Βαθμοί Αναφορές Διακριτικά Περισσότερα ▾

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WN1: Holistic PM competences →

Activities: 5 Πρόοδος: 0 / 4

WN2: Digital skills competences for PM →

Activities: 5 Πρόοδος: 0 / 4

WN3: Green skills competences for PM →

Activities: 5 Πρόοδος: 0 / 4

WN4: Resilience competences for PM →

Activities: 5 Πρόοδος: 0 / 4

WN5: Innovation & entrepreneurship competences →

Activities: 5 Πρόοδος: 0 / 4

WN6: Relearning how to learn in a digital environment →

Activities: 5 Πρόοδος: 0 / 4

Completion →

Activities: 2 Πρόοδος: 0 / 1

Εικόνα 6: Μάθημα WN και οι ενότητες του

The screenshot shows the PreMETS platform interface. On the left, there is a navigation menu with a search icon and a list of course units. The selected unit is 'TN6: Video Lecture'. The main content area on the right features a banner for the 'EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM' with a profile picture of a woman. Below the banner is a video lecture player with a play button. Underneath the player, there is a list of course materials and quizzes for TN6, including 'Material', 'Practise Quiz', and 'Final Quiz'. Each item has a lock icon and a 'Μη διαθέσιμο εκτός αν: Η δραστηριότητα TN6: Video Lecture with Instructor...' or 'TN6: Practise Quiz είναι επισημασμένη...' message, along with a 'Εμφάνιση περισσότερων' link.

Εικόνα 7: Δραστηριότητες ενότητας TN6

Κάθε ενότητα μαθήματος περιλαμβάνει (Εικόνα 7):

- Διαλέξεις βίντεο: Κάθε ενότητα περιέχει ένα βίντεο που εξηγεί βασικές έννοιες. Σε ορισμένες περιπτώσεις, τα βίντεο παρουσιάζουν έναν εκπαιδευτή που παρουσιάζει το υλικό.
- Υλικό μαθήματος (Εικόνα 8): Κάθε ενότητα συνοδεύεται από υλικό με δυνατότητα λήψης, όπως φυλλάδια, διαφάνειες, σενάρια και διαδικτυακές αναζητήσεις, διαθέσιμα σε όλες τις υποστηριζόμενες γλώσσες.
- Κουίζ: Κάθε ενότητα περιλαμβάνει δύο τύπους κουίζ:
 - Κουίζ Εξάσκησης: Περιλαμβάνει 5 τυχαίες ερωτήσεις, όπου οι μαθητές λαμβάνουν ανατροφοδότηση αμέσως μετά την υποβολή. Δεν καταγράφεται βαθμολογία για το κουίζ εξάσκησης.
 - Τελικό Κουίζ: Περιέχει 10 τυχαίες ερωτήσεις από το περιεχόμενο της ενότητας. Δεν παρέχεται ανατροφοδότηση και οι εκπαιδευόμενοι πρέπει να επιτύχουν έναν επιτυχή βαθμό για να προχωρήσουν. Αυτό το κουίζ είναι απαραίτητο για την ολοκλήρωση του μαθήματος
- Πιστοποίηση: Μετά τη διαδικασία εκμάθησης και την επιτυχία του τελικού κουίζ, οι χρήστες λαμβάνουν πιστοποιητικό ολοκλήρωσης για τη συγκεκριμένη ενότητα.

The screenshot shows the PreMETS platform interface. On the left is a navigation menu with categories like 'General', 'TN1: Learner happiness, moti...', and 'TN2: Reducing the percentag...'. The main content area displays the 'TN1: Material' folder structure. At the top, there is a 'Mark as done' button and a 'Download folder' button. Below these, a folder tree lists files for various languages: Deutsch, English, Italiano, Nederlands, Română, Srpski, and Ελληνικά. Each language folder contains files for 'Booklet', 'Slides', 'Storyboard', and 'WebQuest'. A small question mark icon is visible on the right side of the folder tree.

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Εικόνα 8: Φάκελος υλικού TN1

Όλο το εκπαιδευτικό υλικό της πλατφόρμας PreMETS αδειοδοτούνται βάσει της Διεθνούς Άδειας Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0, επιτρέποντας στους χρήστες να έχουν ελεύθερη πρόσβαση και να μοιράζονται το περιεχόμενο με την κατάλληλη απόδοση, αλλά όχι για εμπορικούς σκοπούς και χωρίς τη δυνατότητα τροποποίησης του υλικού.

Με την ολοκλήρωση όλων των ενότητων είτε του μαθήματος TN είτε του WN, οι χρήστες θα ξεκλειδώσουν μια νέα ενότητα που περιέχει ένα τελικό ολοκληρωμένο κουίζ. Αυτό το τελικό κουίζ περιλαμβάνει 25 τυχαίες ερωτήσεις επιλεγμένες από όλες τις ενότητες του μαθήματος. Η επιτυχής ολοκλήρωση του τελικού κουίζ απαιτείται για να λάβει ο εκπαιδευόμενος την πιστοποίηση του τελικού μαθήματος.

Αφού περάσουν το τελικό κουίζ, οι μαθητές θα λάβουν μια πιστοποίηση που περιλαμβάνει το πλήρες όνομά τους, το όνομα του μαθήματος, τον τίτλο της ενότητας (εάν υπάρχει), το όνομα του μαθήματος, την ημερομηνία έκδοσης, έναν κωδικό επαλήθευσης και έναν κωδικό QR. Ο κωδικός QR επιτρέπει την εύκολη επαλήθευση των πιστοποιητικών χρησιμοποιώντας κινητές συσκευές. Όλα τα πιστοποιητικά μπορούν να επικυρωθούν μέσω της πλατφόρμας PreMETS για να επιβεβαιωθεί η γνησιότητά τους (Εικόνα 9).

Εικόνα 9: Υπόδειγμα πιστοποιητικού

Τα μαθήματα στην πλατφόρμα PreMETS περιλαμβάνουν έναν πίνακα ανακοινώσεων (Εικόνα 10) και ένα φόρουμ (Εικόνα 11). Ο πίνακας ανακοινώσεων επιτρέπει σε εκπαιδευτές ή διαχειριστές πλατφόρμας να μοιράζονται σημαντικές ενημερώσεις, ειδοποιήσεις και ειδήσεις σχετικά με τα μαθήματα με τους χρήστες. Το φόρουμ συζήτησης παρέχει έναν διαδραστικό χώρο όπου οι μαθητές μπορούν να επικοινωνούν με άλλους μαθητές και εκπαιδευτές, να κάνουν ερωτήσεις, να ανταλλάσσουν ιδέες και να συμμετέχουν σε συνεργατική μάθηση.

PreMETS Αρχική Ταμπλό Τα μαθήματά μου

TN / Γενικά / Ανακοινώσεις

Ανακοινώσεις

Φόρουμ Εγγραφές Αναφορές Εξαγωγή Περισσότερα

General news and announcements

Αναζήτηση στα φόρουμ Προσθήκη νέου θέματος συζήτησης

Συζήτηση	Εκκίνηση από	Τελευταία ανάρτηση	Απαντήσεις
☆ PreMETS Certification	Afroditi Anagnos... 17 Οκτ 2024	Afroditi Anagnos... 17 Οκτ 2024	0
☆ Train-the-Trainers Pre-Pilot 14-18/10/2024	Afroditi Anagnos... 15 Οκτ 2024	Afroditi Anagnos... 15 Οκτ 2024	0

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Εικόνα 10: Ανακοινώσεις μαθήματος TN

PreMETS Αρχική Ταμπλό Τα μαθήματά μου

TN / Γενικά / Forum

Forum

Φόρουμ Εγγραφές Αναφορές Εξαγωγή Περισσότερα

Αναζήτηση στα φόρουμ Προσθήκη νέου θέματος συζήτησης

Εγγραφείτε σε αυτό το φόρουμ

Συζήτηση	Εκκίνηση από	Τελευταία ανάρτηση	Απαντήσεις	Εγγραφείτε
☆ Questions for TN5-TN8	Afroditi Anagnos... 15 Οκτ 2024	Afroditi Anagnos... 15 Οκτ 2024	0	<input type="checkbox"/>
☆ Questions for TN1 - TN4	Afroditi Anagnos... 15 Οκτ 2024	Afroditi Anagnos... 15 Οκτ 2024	0	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

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Εικόνα 11: Forum μαθήματος TN

4. Πλατφόρμα

Η πλατφόρμα PreMETS προσφέρει μια σειρά χαρακτηριστικών που έχουν σχεδιαστεί για να υποστηρίζουν τόσο τη μάθηση όσο και την αλληλεπίδραση με τον χρήστη:

Κάθε εγγεγραμμένος χρήστης έχει μια εξατομικευμένη σελίδα προφίλ (Εικόνα 12), όπου μπορεί:

- Προβολή και επεξεργασία προσωπικών στοιχείων (όπως όνομα, διεύθυνση email, κ.λπ.).
- Λήψη πιστοποιητικών για ολοκληρωμένα μαθήματα.
- Ζητήστε όλα τα δεδομένα που συλλέγονται από την πλατφόρμα σχετικά με τη δραστηριότητά τους.
- Διαγραφή προσωπικών δεδομένων: Οι χρήστες μπορούν να επιλέξουν να διαγράψουν τον λογαριασμό τους και όλα τα σχετικά δεδομένα, αν και κάτι τέτοιο θα καταργήσει επίσης τη δυνατότητα επαλήθευσης τυχόν πιστοποιήσεων.

The screenshot displays the 'PreMETS Administrator' profile page. At the top, there is a navigation bar with 'PreMETS', 'Home', 'Dashboard', 'My courses', and 'Site administration'. A user profile card shows 'PA' and 'PreMETS Administrator'. Below this, several panels provide user information: 'User details' (with an 'Edit profile' link), 'Miscellaneous' (Notes, My certificates, Forum posts, Forum discussions, Learning plans), 'Reports' (Today's logs, All logs, Outline report, Complete report, Browser sessions, Grades overview, Grades), 'Login activity' (First access to site: Friday, 19 July 2024, 3:27 PM (240 days 22 hours); Last access to site: Monday, 17 March 2025, 1:22 PM (now); Last IP address: 172.71.144.35), 'Mobile app' (QR code for mobile app access, Last access to site: Friday, 8 November 2024, 8:03 AM (129 days 5 hours)), 'Privacy and policies' (Contact the privacy officer, Data requests, Export all of my personal data, Policies and agreements), and 'Course details' (Course profiles: TN: Train-the-Trainer, WN: Predictive Maintenance).

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Εικόνα 12: Παράδειγμα σελίδας προφίλ με επιλογές και πληροφορίες χρήστη

Η πλατφόρμα περιλαμβάνει έναν πίνακα γενικών ανακοινώσεων όπου οι χρήστες μπορούν να βλέπουν ενημερώσεις και σημαντικές ειδοποιήσεις που δημοσιεύονται από διαχειριστές πλατφόρμας ή εκπαιδευτές μαθημάτων. Αυτή η δυνατότητα βοηθά τους χρήστες να ενημερώνονται για νέο περιεχόμενο, επερχόμενες εκδηλώσεις ή ειδήσεις που σχετίζονται με την πλατφόρμα.

Ημερολόγιο Εκδηλώσεων

Το ημερολόγιο εμφανίζει όλα τα σχετικά συμβάντα, όπως τις επερχόμενες προθεσμίες μαθημάτων, τα διαδικτυακά σεμινάρια και τα προγράμματα συντήρησης του συστήματος (Εικόνα 13). Οι χρήστες μπορούν να έχουν πρόσβαση σε αυτό το ημερολόγιο για να ενημερώνονται για σημαντικές ημερομηνίες.

Εικόνα 13: Παράδειγμα συμβάντος ημερολογίου, «WN - Pre-Pilot Timisoara Day 3»

Προσβασιμότητα και πολύγλωσση υποστήριξη

Το PreMETS έχει σχεδιαστεί για να είναι φιλικό προς την προσβασιμότητα, με εργαλεία και χαρακτηριστικά που επαληθεύονται από εξωτερικούς ελέγχους προσβασιμότητας. Η πλατφόρμα υποστηρίζει ένα ευρύ φάσμα αναγκών προσβασιμότητας, συμπεριλαμβανομένων προγραμμάτων ανάγνωσης οθόνης και εναλλακτικών επιλογών πλοήγησης.

Επιπλέον, οι χρήστες μπορούν να επιλέξουν τη γλώσσα που προτιμούν μέσω του μενού γλώσσας της πλατφόρμας. Ενώ τα αγγλικά υποστηρίζονται πλήρως, ένα σημαντικό μέρος του περιεχομένου της πλατφόρμας μεταφράζεται σε άλλες γλώσσες. Αυτό βοηθά να διασφαλιστεί ότι η πλατφόρμα είναι προσβάσιμη σε χρήστες από διάφορα γλωσσικά υπόβαθρα.

Η πλατφόρμα διέπεται από τρεις κύριες πολιτικές: τους Όρους Χρήσης, την Πολιτική Cookies και την Πολιτική Απορρήτου.

- Οι Όροι Χρήσης περιγράφουν τους κανόνες και τις οδηγίες που πρέπει να ακολουθούν οι χρήστες κατά την πρόσβαση ή τη χρήση της πλατφόρμας. Καλύπτει τις ευθύνες τόσο της πλατφόρμας όσο και του χρήστη, συμπεριλαμβανομένης της αποδεκτής συμπεριφοράς, των περιορισμών στη χρήση και των συνεπειών από την παραβίαση αυτών των όρων. Αντιμετωπίζει επίσης νομικά ζητήματα, όπως δικαιώματα πνευματικής ιδιοκτησίας, αποποίησης ευθυνών και περιορισμούς ευθύνης, λειτουργώντας ουσιαστικά ως συμφωνία μεταξύ του χρήστη και της πλατφόρμας σχετικά με τον τρόπο χρήσης της υπηρεσίας.
- Η Πολιτική Cookies εξηγεί πώς η πλατφόρμα χρησιμοποιεί cookies για να βελτιώσει την εμπειρία του χρήστη. Τα cookies είναι μικρά αρχεία κειμένου που αποθηκεύονται στη συσκευή ενός χρήστη και βοηθούν την πλατφόρμα να θυμάται ορισμένες λεπτομέρειες όπως προτιμήσεις, πληροφορίες

σύνδεσης ή να παρακολουθεί πώς χρησιμοποιείται ο ιστότοπος. Αυτή η πολιτική περιγράφει λεπτομερώς τους τύπους των cookies που χρησιμοποιούνται, τους λόγους χρήσης τους (όπως για λειτουργικότητα ή μάρκετινγκ) και παρέχει οδηγίες στους χρήστες σχετικά με τον τρόπο διαχείρισης ή απενεργοποίησης των cookies στις ρυθμίσεις του προγράμματος περιήγησής τους.

- Η Πολιτική Απορρήτου περιγράφει πώς η πλατφόρμα συλλέγει, αποθηκεύει και προστατεύει τα προσωπικά δεδομένα των χρηστών. Εξηγεί τους τύπους των προσωπικών πληροφοριών που συλλέγονται, όπως ονόματα, διευθύνσεις email ή στοιχεία πληρωμής, και πώς χρησιμοποιούνται αυτές οι πληροφορίες, είτε για τη βελτίωση των υπηρεσιών είτε για την επικοινωνία. Η πολιτική εξετάζει επίσης τον τρόπο με τον οποίο η πλατφόρμα μπορεί να μοιράζεται δεδομένα με τρίτους και ενημερώνει τους χρήστες για τα δικαιώματά τους πρόσβασης, ενημέρωσης ή διαγραφής των προσωπικών τους στοιχείων.

Όλες οι πολιτικές παρατίθενται στον ακόλουθο σύνδεσμο:
<https://premets-platform.eu/admin/tool/policy/viewall.php>

5. Συμπεράσματα

Η πλατφόρμα PreMETS είναι ένα ολοκληρωμένο και φιλικό προς τον χρήστη περιβάλλον που προσφέρει εκπαίδευση υψηλής ποιότητας στην Προγνωστική Συντήρηση. Με μια διαισθητική διεπαφή, ποικίλους πόρους εκμάθησης και μια σειρά διαδραστικών χαρακτηριστικών, το PreMETS επιτρέπει στους μαθητές να αναπτύξουν κρίσιμες δεξιότητες σε ένα συνεργατικό και ελκυστικό περιβάλλον.

Ακολουθώντας αυτό το εγχειρίδιο, οι χρήστες μπορούν εύκολα να πλοηγηθούν στην πλατφόρμα, να αποκτήσουν πρόσβαση σε μαθήματα, να ολοκληρώσουν κουίζ και να λάβουν πολύτιμες πιστοποιήσεις μετά την ολοκλήρωση του μαθήματος. Είτε εκπαιδευόμενος, εκπαιδευτής ή διαχειριστής πλατφόρμας, το PreMETS παρέχει όλα τα απαραίτητα εργαλεία για μια επιτυχημένη εκπαιδευτική εμπειρία.